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Perioperative chemotherapy versus surgery alone for resectable colorectal liver metastases: an international multicentre propensity score matched analysis on long-term outcomes according to established prognostic risk scores --Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:	HPB-D-20-00324R1
Full Title:	Perioperative chemotherapy versus surgery alone for resectable colorectal liver metastases: an international multicentre propensity score matched analysis on long-term outcomes according to established prognostic risk scores
Article Type:	Original Article
Keywords:	Liver metastases, colorectal cancer, liver resection, chemotherapy, colorectal liver metastases
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Abstract:	<p>Background: There is still uncertainty regarding the role of perioperative chemotherapy (CTx) in patients with resectable colorectal liver metastases (CRLM), especially in those with a low-risk of recurrence.</p> <p>Methods: Multicentre retrospective analysis of patients with CRLM undergoing liver resection between 2010-2015. Patients were divided into two groups according to whether they received perioperative CTx or not and were compared using propensity score matching (PSM) analysis. Then, they were stratified according to prognostic risk scores, including: Clinical Risk Score (CRS), Tumour Burden Score (TBS) and Genetic And Morphological Evaluation (GAME) score.</p> <p>Results: The study included 967 patients with a median follow-up of 68 months. After PSM analysis, patients with perioperative CTx presented prolonged overall survival (OS) in comparison with the surgery alone group (82.8 vs 52.5 months, p=0.017). On multivariate analysis perioperative CTx was an independent predictor of increased OS (HR 0.705, 95%CI 0.705-0.516, p=0.029). The benefits of perioperative CTx on survival were confirmed in patients with CRS and TBS scores ≤ 2 (p=0.022 and p=0.020, respectively) and in patients with a GAME score ≤ 1 (p=0.006).</p> <p>Conclusion: Perioperative CTx demonstrated an increase in OS in patients with CRLM. Patients with a low-risk of recurrence seem to benefit from systemic treatment.</p>
Suggested Reviewers:	<p>Benedetto Ielpo, PhD Attending HPB Surgeon, Hospital del Mar Institute for Medical Research: Institut Hospital del Mar d'Investigacions Mediques ielpo.b@gmail.com Expertise in HPB and liver surgery.</p> <p>Stijn van Laarhoven Attending HPB Surgeon, University Hospitals Bristol and Weston NHS Foundation Trust svlaarhoven@gmail.com Expertise in HPB and liver surgery.</p>
Opposed Reviewers:	
Additional Information:	
Question	Response
Please state the word count of your submission	2881
Please state how many references appear in the reference list.	35

Reviewer 1: The authors investigate the role of perioperative chemotherapy in patients with resectable CRLM using a propensity score matching analysis. This is a multicenter study. The manuscript is well written, statistics are solid and well performed. Conclusions are balanced and supported by the data. I enjoyed reading the paper and i believe that the clinical question is well posed in the current literature. I sincerely appreciated the deep discussion of the limitations of the study which is frequently missed in scientific papers. Retrospective studies are limited as the authors mentioned and although PSM is a good method to try decrease this limitation, authors frequently forget that this method is actually increasing selection of patients. With PSM you lose patients in order to "adjust" by necessity your population to the group that has the most rare characteristics. As an example: in PSM studies comparing open vs laparoscopy, you always lose more patients in the open group to retrieve a number of patients that has characteristics closer to the laparoscopic group. By doing this you are excluding difficult resections, cholangiocarcinoma, vessel reconstructions. So you are ultra selecting. The authors could briefly comment on this. As a result of this process, you get to the point were the main limitation in your results is indeed in the lack of reliability in the analysis of the high-risk patients. You have a low number of patients in this group because you lost them all after PSM. Indeed, high risk patients normally will have chemotherapy while surgery alone is generally reserved to patients with low risk features. So i guess that the authors could further describe the characteristics of those 30ish high risk patients who did not undergo chemotherapy. Why? Age? Comorbidities? or other factors? Finally, have the authors tried to compare patients undergoing surgery alone vs surgery + adjuvant chemotherapy only? Can some more information be retrieved by this analysis? Overall i want to congratulate the authors for the manuscript which i believe is a nice piece of work.

Reply Reviewer 1

We would like to thank the reviewer for his/her comments and for the opportunity to improve the quality of our manuscript. We acknowledge that the PSM while trying to homogenise study and control group for confounding can favour a potential selection bias, as nicely stated above by the reviewer. Therefore, we have modified the text according to the reviewer comment and added a more detailed description of those high-risk patients.

Regarding the comparison between surgery alone vs surgery + adjuvant chemotherapy only this is an extremely interesting topic that we have discussed in depth during the elaboration of the manuscript. Data on different regimen of perioperative CTx, as well as length and type of CTx have been assessed, however, we decided that this analysis was beyond the scope of the present paper. These findings will be included in future publications focused on this issue. The would like to thank again the reviewer for their comment and suggestion.

Reviewer 2: The authors address the crucial topic of whether perioperative chemotherapy is beneficial in patients with colorectal liver metastases, using propensity-score matching to simulate randomization in an attempt to minimize inherent selection bias in this retrospective multiinstitutional series. Several comments

METHODS

The authors recognize the potential for bias given the retrospective nature of the data and multiinstitutional/international group of centers participating. Can the authors provide information on the number of participating studies, patients per center contributed

The variation in chemotherapy regimens is also notable; the authors note in the tables "patients receiving at least two chemotherapy drugs". Is any further information available on the heterogeneity of chemo regimens?

The PSM model used here seems to primarily exclude high-risk patients. Table 1 shows that perioperative chemotherapy was offered to 779 patients with 188 going to surgery alone; PSM analysis included 175 patients with periop chemotherapy and 175 patients undergoing surgery alone. The authors note the significant differences in the groups prior to PSM, with the group undergoing perioperative chemotherapy having significantly more advanced tumors (higher T/N stage, more bilobar, more synchronous and multifocal, more often major hepatectomy or hepatectomy + ablation, etc...). In order to match the cohorts, this means that 604 patients were excluded from the periop chemo group and only 13 from the surgery alone group. As a result, this study primarily focuses on low-risk groups. The authors do bring attention to this in the manuscript but this should be further discussed, the data do not support benefits of periop chemo in higher-risk patients.

Please clarify numbers of patients undergoing periop therapy in total; 779 patients in total included 594 patients treated with neoadjuvant therapy, 508 treated with adjuvant therapy, 308 with pre/post chemotherapy. Would this not mean that the total of chemotherapy patients should be (594+508-308) 794 patients? Please clarify

The authors state in the methods that "prior to PSM analysis, missing data were multiply imputed using multivariate chained equations...." Missing data are certainly common with the retrospective, multiinstitutional nature of the study, though the use of imputed data is a potential source of bias. As the general purpose of PSM is to reduce imbalances in outcome-related variables, further information on the extent of data imputation seems warranted. Whether this is a potential limitation of the study should be addressed

RESULTS

Can the authors comment on the RO rate of 60%? with R2 resections excluded, this implies a 40% R1 rate despite stated intention (in methods) for margin-negative resection. Was this consistent across centers? The PSM model used does not include R status. While this was equivalent pre-matching (Table 2), did this remain consistent after matching?

The authors note increased overall survival in the chemotherapy group after PSM, and cite "an increase in RFS in the Ctx group, although this does not reach statistical significance (RFS 35.6 mos vs 31 mos p=0.209). This should not be presented as an increase in RFS as it was statistically insignificant

DISCUSSION

The authors should give more attention to the fact that this is essentially a comparison of lower-risk groups (noted above) with data that can not be extrapolated to the higher-risk population

Discussing limitations of the study, authors correctly acknowledge the possibility of patients who progress on perioperative CTx who do not get to surgery. Are there any data from the centers included on these patients?

The authors should discuss why there is no statistically significant difference in RFS but there is in OS between groups

Reply Reviewer 2

We would like to thank the reviewer for his/her comments and for the opportunity to improve the quality of our manuscript.

METHODS

- Comment on number of cases per year provided by each centre have been added.
- We acknowledge that the variation in chemotherapy regimens is also notable. While the table present a summarized information on CTx, in the text we detailed the type of CTx as well as the percentage of patients receiving each regimen.
“FOLFOX (folinic acid, 5-FU and oxaliplatin) was given to 46.5% of patients receiving CTx. Other regimens were a combination of FOLFIRI (folinic acid, 5-FU and irinotecan) given to 18.2% of patients receiving CTx; XELOX (capecitabine and oxaliplatin) given to 14.5%; LV5FU2 (leucovorin and 5-FU) given to 6.7%; UFT (uracil and tegafur) given to 3.8%. Eighty-five percent of patients receiving CTx were given at least six cycles.”
- This issue has also been mentioned by Reviewer 1. As stated above we have highlighted the limitations of the present study in regards with high-risk patients and added a more detailed description of those high-risk patients.
- We thank the reviewer for noticing the numbers of neoadjuvant, adjuvant and perioperative CTx did not sum up correctly. We double checked our data and the correct number of patients undergoing perioperative CTx is 323 (594+508-323=779). We modified the paper. Thanks.
- As stated by the reviewer, the concept that “the use of imputed data is a potential source of bias” is certainly a valid concern, especially if the data were not missing at random. Before imputing the data, we performed a Little’s test for missing completely at random (MCAR) test on imputed variables. The test showed that the MCAR assumption was satisfied ($p=1.000$). Furthermore, we used $M=50$ multiple imputations (despite the fact that some research statisticians have recommended that only $M=5$ imputations are needed to get stable estimates). Therefore, and since the data appear to be missing at random (based on Little’s test for MCAR the applied imputation is unlikely to introduce bias in the used dataset. This concept has been added to the manuscript.

RESULTS

- Regarding the high R1 rate, we double checked our database and R0/R1 was consistent among centres included in the study. As shown in table 4 this rate remained consistent after the PSM. We acknowledge that this R1 rate seem pretty high, however, it must be taken into account that: a) included centres used a parenchyma sparing liver approach; b) this number of R1 includes R1vascular (tumour detached from vascular pedicles, whose survival has been shown to be comparable with R0¹); c) 53.5% patients included in our series presented multiple CRLM, being 36.7% of them bilobar, which increase the chance of having an R1 resection, at least in one of the resected lesions.
- References to the differences in RFS between the CTx and surgery alone group have been modified emphasizing the lack of statistical differences when RFS was analysed.

DISCUSSION

- As commented above, further details on the limitations related to the analysis of high-risk patients have been added.
- Unfortunately, the dataset included only patients who did not progress under CTx, we do not have data of patients did not respond to preoperative CTx. This would be an interesting topic for future research. Thanks.
- As it can be seen in the modified table 3 (added according to reviewers' comments) several factors were associated with decreased RFS and OS. However, perioperative CTx represented an independent predictor of both RFS and OS in the multivariable model from the unmatched cohort. The lack of statistical differences in the matched cohort could be related to a shorter median RFS in comparison with OS and a lack of statistical power to identify significant statistical differences. Additionally, our definition of recurrence was quite broad, including both liver and extrahepatic disease, as well as early and delayed recurrences. Despite our efforts to homogenise groups with the PSM and the stratification according to clinical risk score, the lack of statistical difference in RFS could still be influenced by an imbalance in some of these characteristics in the control and study group influencing the RFS.

Reviewer 3: Thank you for the opportunity to review this paper describing the results of a propensity matched comparison of perioperative therapy compared to no chemotherapy for resection of colorectal liver metastases (CRLM). The authors used a multi-institutional dataset of 967 patients undergoing resection of CRLM to match those receiving perioperative chemotherapy to those not receiving it and compared survival outcomes. They further compared survival by stratifying the matched cohort by risk of recurrence using 3 different prognostication scores. They conclude that there is an association between receipt of perioperative chemotherapy and improved survival.

I have a few comments and questions re the analysis to better understand how the analysis was designed and conducted that if addressed would bring clarity to the how the results should be interpreted and whether they are novel.

METHODS

- the authors combine pre-operative and adjuvant therapy together to examine the association of chemotherapy and survival. The use of pre vs post-op chemotherapy is very different and may not bring the same rationale to benefit survival. Can the authors explain how this choice was made and what this means for the results? could the analysis have been stratified by chemotherapy regimens such that pre and post-op chemo groups are examined separately?
- The cohort includes patients operated from 2010 to 2015, such that the cohort is not truly contemporary. How could this have affected the results? especially with regards to systemic therapy regimens and patterns of care. were temporal changes over the study period considered in the analysis?
- Outcome: further details are required re the definition of OS and RFS. how was recurrence defined? what censoring was used? how long were the patients followed? what was the minimum opportunity for follow-up in all patients (what was the end of study date to capture the outcome)?
- Missing data: multiple imputation was used. Multiple imputation may not be appropriate in all cases depending on the patterns of missing data. In particular information on mutational analysis (necessary for the GAME score) is often missing very frequently making imputation of this variable inappropriate. Please provide information re missing data - what variables were imputed and what was the % missingness for each variable? was the missingness random or not random, i.e. associated or not with the outcome and with the exposure?
- Propensity score for matching: I understand that the PS was used to match on the likelihood of receiving chemo vs not. Therefore, only variables available at the time of deciding on giving chemo should be included - those are all pre-operative variables. However variables such as intraop ablation are included. Please also indicate how tumor size and number was captured and when - is it on initial imaging or on pathology (which is not info available when deciding on treatment and can be influenced by receipt of preop chemo)?
- Balancing measures to assess the quality of the matching should be described in the methods. This typically would include standardized mean differences on variables included

in the PS as well as plots looking at matching of continuous variables and distribution of the PS.

- The objective and stated novelty of this work is to assess the impact of chemo on survival across prognostication groups. However, this analysis is only reported on quickly at the end. Shouldn't this be the main focus of the paper? Also, this stratified analysis is not presented in the methods.

RESULTS

- To better understand the power of the analysis and fit of the model, please report number of events (deaths and recurrences) over the study period for the entire cohort, matched cohort, as well as sub-groups by prognostic scores.

- Please provide dispersion measures when reporting on median follow-up and survival (range or IQR).

- Table 5: It is not clear to me how the models were constructed for MVA. Does table 5 report MVA in the entire or the matched cohort?

* The aim was to assess the association between chemo and survival. Therefore, a main effect model should be presented, showing the adjusted HR for chemo vs no chemo adjusted for other variables. HR on other variables aren't informative.

* why were complications included in the model? This is problematic because it is on the causal pathway. In addition, Clavien-Dindo grade $\geq 3A$ includes grade 5 which is death and death is the outcome of the model.

* why was N stage included in the model if this was performed in the matched cohort? N stage was included in the PS so should not be further adjusted for in the MVA.

- Survival figures: please consider stopping the curves at 5 years. Beyond that time, the numbers at risk become very small and estimates are likely unstable.

DISCUSSION

- the authors state that the PSM analysis approximates a randomized study. This is not true and is a very debated topic. No retrospective study design can approximate a RCT. There will always be unmeasured confounding. Could the authors address the extent of residual confounding in their results?

- Language referring to causality between chemo and survival should be avoided, such as "benefit" or chemo "increasing" survival. With this study design, only associations can be observed.

- The description of the prognostic scores used for the analysis should be presented in the Methods section.

- Can the authors comment on the potential for immortal time bias? How would it impact the results and what was or could have been done to mitigate it? In particular, patients do not all have the same opportunity to have the exposure (chemotherapy) depending on how long they lived after diagnosis and after surgery. This is even more confusing considering that the

exposure includes both preop and postop chemotherapy so the bias would be different for those 2 groups that have been combined.

- It is not clear from the intro and the discussion why this analysis was needed and what it adds to the existing literature. Especially what does it add to existing RCT on this exact topic. Finally, how should these data change practice? what do they mean for clinicians and patients when making decisions re surgery and periop chemotherapy?

We would like to thank the reviewer for his/her comments and for the opportunity to improve the quality of our manuscript.

METHODS

- The decision to compare patients with surgery alone vs perioperative CTx was made due to the lack of level I supporting the utilization of perioperative CTx in the context of CRLM. As described in the introduction section, a pooled analysis of two phase III RCT was not able to prove survival advantages in favour of adjuvant CTx². Similarly, although the first publication of the European Organization for Research and Treatment of Cancer (EORTC) 40983 (EPOC) trial reported improved progression-free survival in patients with resectable CRLM receiving perioperative CTx compared to surgery alone, this did not translate into increased overall survival in the long-term analysis^{3,4}. Despite the lack of level I evidence⁵, perioperative CTx is usually recommended in patients with CRLM⁶⁻⁸. We discussed in depth whether we should have provided data on different regimens of perioperative CTx, as well as on length and type of CTx. However, we decided to focus this manuscript on the role of perioperative CTx in comparison with surgery alone. Further analysis will compare the different regimens or perioperative CTx.

- The cohort includes patients operated on from 2010 to 2015, as we were aiming to obtain a minimum follow-up of five year, in order to assess long term outcomes. Whether it could be argued that this is not truly contemporary, especially with regards to systemic CTx, as described in the results section: *“Perioperative CTx was based mainly on a combination of two drugs for a total minimum duration of three months (six cycles). FOLFOX (folinic acid, 5-FU and oxaliplatin) was given to 46.5% of patients receiving CTx. Other regimens were a combination of FOLFIRI (folinic acid, 5-FU and irinotecan) given to 18.2% of patients receiving CTx; XELOX (capecitabine and oxaliplatin) given to 14.5%; LV5FU2 (leucovorin and 5-FU) given to 6.7%; UFT (uracil and tegafur) given to 3.8%.”* These regimens are modern systemic CTx regimen, currently still used by major institutions treating CRLM. Additionally, the surgical approach in regards with resectable CRLM has not experienced significant changes during the last five years. The major improvement in the surgical technique has been the diffusion of a minimally invasive approach that so far hasn't clearly demonstrated a survival benefit.

- Recurrence was defined as documentation of colorectal metastatic disease either radiologically or by biopsy, after a disease-free interval ≥ 3 months. Disease-free patients were followed for a maximum of ten year. These concepts have been added

to the manuscript. As we included patients operated on until 2015 and the data collection was performed in 2020 with updated follow-up data, the minimum follow-up was 5 year. Survival analysis was performed according to Cox model, as specified in the methodology. Cancer related death and the presence of recurrence were used as “status variables” with right censoring.

- As commented, the concerns regarding the use of imputed data as a potential source of bias are certainly justified. Before imputing the data, we performed a Little’s test for missing completely at random (MCAR) test on imputed variables. The test showed that the MCAR assumption was satisfied ($P=1.000$). Furthermore, we used $M=50$ multiple imputations (despite the fact that some research statisticians have recommended that only $M=5$ imputations are needed to get stable estimates). Therefore, since the data appear to be missing at random (based on Little’s test for MCAR), it should be safe to say that the use of imputed data is unlikely to introduce bias. This concept has been added to the manuscript. Additionally, multiple imputation was used exclusively for building up the PS model. The subgroup analysis according to CRS, TBS and GAME was performed from data presents in the original dataset. Further details on multiple imputations have been added to the manuscript.

- Tumour size and number were captured on preoperative images. As stated in the manuscript: “*The final model consisted of the following covariates: age, gender, ASA classification, comorbidities, bilirubin, albumin, creatinine and CEA levels, the T and N stage of colorectal cancer, interval time between primary tumour resection and diagnosis of CRLM, the size and number of liver metastases, previous liver resection, the type and extent of resection, concomitant ablation procedures, the tumour grade, and KRAS mutational status*”.

The expression “the size and number of liver metastases as determined by preoperative imaging” has been added. The PSM was performed to balance study and control group, minimising confounding influencing survival. Even if some of these variables were not available at the time of deciding on giving chemo, they represented confounding influencing survival in study and control group, as shown by the univariate analysis.

- In order to assess the quality of the matching we provided as supplementary material: a) Figure describing the discrimination of propensity-score model (AUC 0.8); b) Figure describing the calibration of the matching according to Hosmer-Lemeshow test: $c2 = 10.60$, $P = 0.3899$; c) Figures with a visual distribution of the propensity-score before and after the matching. The idea to report SMD is certainly a valid one, and some PSM studies do indeed report the SMD. However, the use and interpretation of the SMD can be problematic too: it’s best (and least controversially) used when the imputed variables are continuous and follow a normal distribution (because the SMD statistic is somewhat predicated on assumption of normality). However, we imputed a variety of variables—continuous variables (which were not necessarily normally-distributed) were imputed using the K-nearest neighbors method, and we also imputed multinomial/ordered categorical variables using logistic regression, and also imputed count variables using Poisson regression. As such, the idea to report SMD may not be so appropriate for our study where we have included binary/categorical variables, count variables, and non-normal continuous variables—and it is arguably not very

interpretable nor appropriate to analyse the SMD of such variables (since the calculation and interpretation of SMD requires that the imputed variables are all normally-distributed continuous variables).

- The main aim of the paper is to describe outcomes of surgery alone vs surgery with perioperative CTx in homogenous groups of patients stratified according to validated prognostic risk scores. The second paragraph of the results section focuses on the comparison of surgery vs perioperative CTx before and after the matching. The third one reports the subgroup analysis according to prognostic scores. While the second paragraph already demonstrates the possible advantage of perioperative CTx, the third one goes even further assessing these outcomes in low- and high-risk of recurrence patients. The association showed in the entire cohort is confirmed in the low-risk subgroups, but not in the high-risk groups (possible limitations of this analysis have been described in the discussion section). Several papers have described the potential advantages of perioperative CTx in high-risk patients, however the novelty of this paper is the evaluation of the perioperative CTx in homogenous groups of low-risk risk patients.

RESULTS

- Number of events and dispersions measurers for death, recurrences, RFS and OS are provided in table 2 and 4 and in figures 2-4-5-6.

- We would like to thank the reviewer for its comment on the multivariable analysis as it has helped us to realise that the multivariable model should have been improved. This analysis is based on unmatched subjects; therefore, we have decided to change the previous Table 5 to Table 3.

Now this modified table reports a bivariable analysis assessing factors associated with worse RFS and and OS. Variables significant on this bivariable analysis are included in the multivariable model. Additional comments have been added to the Methods section.

- We thank the reviewer for his suggestion and we acknowledge the fact that beyond 5-year numbers at risk become very small, thus not that relevant from a statistical point of view. However, as the main aim of the paper was to assess long-term oncological outcomes, we would prefer to keep the figures showing the number at risk after 5-years as it is a way to illustrate the proportion of patients at risk, during the follow-up.

DISCUSSION

- We acknowledge that no retrospective study can approximate a RCT. As commented above in regards with comments made by other reviewers, references in the manuscript to this concept have been modified. To the best of our abilities, we have included most prognostic variables into the propensity score model already, so this should hopefully minimize residual confounding.

- Refences to causality between chemo and survival in the discussion have been smoothed or modified.

- The material and methods section include references to the original articles describing the prognostic scores: “*Then, they were stratified according to widely used prognostic risk scores for recurrence cited by the vast majority of the most recent consensus papers and clinical guidelines including the Clinical Risk Score (CRS) (19), the Tumour Burden Score (20) and the Genetic And Morphological Evaluation (GAME) score (21).*” As the paper already includes 6 figures, 6 tables, 4 suppl. Figures and 1 supplementary table, we preferred not to add more additional tables, but to cite the original articles describing the prognostic scores.

- Perioperative deaths were excluded from the survival analysis (This concept has been added to the manuscript). As nicely stated by the reviewer, the immortal bias is certainly an important type to consider in this kind of studies. The administration of CTx after the surgical procedure could be influenced by post-operative complications: the presence of severe post-operative complication could cause indeed a lack in CTx administration. However, median length of stay was 6 days (IQR 5-8 and 5-9) and very few patients presented severe post-operative complications, precluding the administration of CTx. In the surgery alone group only 2 patients experienced a post-operative liver failure and 6 bile leaks (Table 2). Additionally, no significant differences are noted when post-operative complications are assessed. Therefore, it is unlikely that these factors could have significantly influenced the lack of CTx administration in the surgery alone group.

- As commented above, the main aim of the paper is to describe outcomes of surgery alone vs surgery with perioperative CTx in homogenous groups of patients stratified according to validated prognostic risk scores. In clinical practice, the combination of surgery and CTx is increasingly accepted as treatment for resectable CRLM. However, there is a paucity of level I evidence studies assessing the long-term outcomes of resected CRLM that support these recommendations. We firstly demonstrated the benefit of perioperative CTx, and then we assessed these outcomes in low- and high-risk of recurrence patients. While the association between CTx and increased survival is demonstrated in the low-risk subgroups, this association cannot be confirmed in the high-risk groups for the limitations described in the discussion. Several papers have described the advantages of the perioperative CTx in high-risk patients, however the novelty of this paper is the demonstration that homogenous patients included in low-risk category present longer survival when treated with CTx in addition to surgery. Therefore, this paper provides a solid background for clinical guidelines on CRLM.

Reviewer 4: Thank you for the opportunity to review this nice manuscript. While we do have randomized data in this space, I think this manuscript is quite valuable in 1) incorporating real-world, multi-center practices and outcomes, outside of highly selected patients in clinic trials, 2) incorporating more sophisticated propensity scoring, and 3) it included stratification of patients by risk of recurrence. I have the following comments/questions:

1. Was volumetry performed in every case? The authors define resectable as an FLR of 25-30%, but that only helps if liver volumes are measured in every patient. One can envision that, despite every effort to homogenize this cohort, there was still variability about what was considered resectable--and this could significantly influence your results.
2. The authors state that an MRI was 'usually' performed. Obviously it would be ideal if that number was 100%, but are we talking 60% or 90%? Gets to the question, again, of variability within the cohort.
3. Can the authors discuss why they think OS was different in the PSM matched groups, but not RFS? Feels odd

Reply Reviewer 3

We would like to thank the reviewer for his/her comments and for the opportunity to improve the quality of our manuscript.

- Volumetry was not performed in every case but only in those patients with extended/two stages resections, at risk of post-operative liver failure. As the reviewer correctly state, despite every effort to homogenize this cohort, there was still variability about what CRLM was considered resectable. This limitation is well described in our discussion: *“Furthermore, it must be considered that, there is not a universally accepted definition of borderline resectable borderline CRLM, that might slightly differ between centres included in our study. Accordingly, we have tried to apply the lowest common denominator by defining resectability only by a future liver remnant of 25%, a definition that is commonly accepted by many experienced hepatobiliary surgeons.”* Unfortunately, this variability cannot be avoided in a multicentric, retrospective study design on liver resection for CRLM resection.
- Preoperative evaluation was performed according to each centre protocol. Unfortunately we do not have precise data on the exact percentage of MRI performed. Data on preoperative number and size of patients were recorded from preoperative images. Again, as the reviewer correctly states the percentage of preoperative MRI, as many other factors such as the intraoperative diagnosis of new lesions with IO-US, the presence of disappearing lesions after neoadjuvant CTx, etc... could have influenced outcomes. This is a common problem of studies related to CRLM. However, the matched analysis and the stratification according to three internationally validate prognostic risk-scores represent an attempt to try to homogenise study and control group as much as possible.
- As it can be seen in the modified table 3 (added according to reviewers' comments) several factors were associated with decreased RFS and OS. However, perioperative CTx represented an independent predictor or both RFS and OS in the multivariable model from the unmatched cohort. The lack of statistical

differences in the matched cohort could be related to a shorter median RFS in comparison with OS and a lack of statistical power to identify significant statistical differences. Additionally, our definition of recurrence was quite broad, including both liver and extrahepatic disease, as well as early and delayed recurrences. Despite our efforts to homogenise groups with the PSM and the stratification according to clinical risk score, the lack of statistical difference in RFS could still be influenced by an imbalance in some of these characteristics in the control and study group influencing the RFS.

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Cover Letter for Manuscript Submission

Dr. Marcello Di Martino, M.D. Ph. D.

Dear Editor-in-Chief,

We are writing to submit our manuscript entitled “*Perioperative chemotherapy versus surgery alone for resectable colorectal liver metastases: an international multicentre propensity score matched analysis on long-term outcomes according to established prognostic risk scores*” We would like to have the manuscript considered for publication in HPB as *Original Article*.

This article focuses on the controversy regarding the role of perioperative chemotherapy (CTx) in the context of resectable colorectal liver metastases (CRLM). Despite the lack of level I evidence, the combination of surgery and CTx is increasingly accepted as treatment for resectable CRLM. This multicentric study evaluates the role of perioperative CTx for CRLM assessing differences in long-term oncologic outcomes.

Our database includes a large group of patients coming from several European institutions with patients with a median follow-up of 68 months. In order to obtain homogeneous group of patients a propensity score matched analysis was used. Furthermore, as CRLM can include a wide spectrum of disease, patients were stratified according to internationally validated prognostic risk scores.

This study evaluate one of the largest cohorts of patient with resectable CRLM and demonstrates the advantage of perioperative CTx in resectable CRLM, especially in patients with low risk of recurrence.

This manuscript describes a novel work and is not under consideration for publication/published by any other journal. All authors have approved the manuscript and this submission. The abstract has been accepted as oral presentation for the 33rd Spanish National Congress.

The authors certify that there is no conflict of interest with any financial/research/academic organization, with regards to the content discussed in the manuscript.

Thank you for receiving our manuscript and considering it for review.

Kindly contact us at the following address for any future correspondence.

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TITLE PAGE

TITLE

Perioperative chemotherapy versus surgery alone for resectable colorectal liver metastases: an international multicentre propensity score matched analysis on long-term outcomes according to established prognostic risk scores

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Conflicts of interest: The Authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

Author Contribution

We hereby certify that all listed co-authors were integrally involved in the formation of this manuscript via study conception/design and/or data acquisition and analysis/interpretation. Furthermore, all authors made significant contributions to the drafting or critical revisions of the manuscript, and all authors gave final approval prior to submission for publication.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

They study was approved by our local Ethical Board, register number 3675, on the 7th of March 2019. No grants or other forms of funding or assistance were utilized in the formation of this manuscript.

Perioperative chemotherapy versus surgery alone for resectable colorectal liver metastases: an international multicentre propensity score matched analysis on long-term outcomes according to established prognostic risk scores

ABSTRACT

Background:

There is still uncertainty regarding the role of perioperative chemotherapy (CTx) in patients with resectable colorectal liver metastases (CRLM), especially in those with a low-risk of recurrence.

Methods:

Multicentre retrospective analysis of patients with CRLM undergoing liver resection between 2010-2015. Patients were divided into two groups according to whether they received perioperative CTx or not and were compared using propensity score matching (PSM) analysis. Then, they were stratified according to prognostic risk scores, including: Clinical Risk Score (CRS), Tumour Burden Score (TBS) and Genetic And Morphological Evaluation (GAME) score.

Results:

The study included 967 patients with a median follow-up of 68 months. After PSM analysis, patients with perioperative CTx presented prolonged overall survival (OS) in comparison with the surgery alone group (82.8 vs 52.5 months, $p=0.017$). On multivariable analysis perioperative CTx was an independent predictor of increased OS (HR 0.705, 95%CI 0.705-0.516, $p=0.029$).

The benefits of perioperative CTx on survival were confirmed in patients with CRS and TBS scores ≤ 2 ($p=0.022$ and $p=0.020$, respectively) and in patients with a GAME score ≤ 1 ($p=0.006$).

Conclusion: Perioperative CTx demonstrated an increase in OS in patients with CRLM. Patients with a low-risk of recurrence seem to benefit from systemic treatment.

BACKGROUND:

Colorectal liver metastases (CRLM) is one of the leading causes of death from cancer (1) with a recurrence rate of 50–75% and a 5-year overall survival rate of about 50% in resected patients (2, 3). Liver resection represents the gold standard of treatment for resectable CRLM. While the role of chemotherapy (CTx) in unresectable or borderline resectable CRLM is well established, with the aim of decreasing the patients' tumour burden and achieving a safe liver resection, there is still debate regarding the role of perioperative CTx in the context of resectable CRLM (4, 5).

In clinical practice, the combination of surgery and CTx is increasingly accepted as treatment for resectable CRLM (6-8). However, there is a paucity of level I evidence studies (9) assessing the long-term outcomes of resected CRLM that support these recommendations. Despite several retrospective series suggesting a potential survival benefit for patients with CRLM who underwent liver resection in combination with CTx (10-12), randomised clinical trials (RCT) have not confirmed these findings. A pooled analysis of two phase III RCT was not able to prove survival advantages in favour of adjuvant CTx (13). Similarly, although the first publication of the European Organization for Research and Treatment of Cancer (EORTC) 40983 (EPOC) trial reported improved progression-free survival in patients with resectable CRLM receiving perioperative CTx compared to surgery alone, this did not translate into increased overall survival in the long-term analysis (14, 15). This uncertainty regarding CRLM management may partly be due to the fact that these studies were not well powered to detect minor differences in long-term outcomes, and they often involved a very heterogeneous group of patients not stratified according to the prognostic factors for risk of recurrence. Despite the lack of level I evidence (9), perioperative CTx is usually recommended in patients with CRLM, especially in those with a high risk of recurrence, but there is still significant uncertainty regarding its role in patients with a low risk of recurrence (6-8).

The aim of this study is to evaluate the role of perioperative CTx for CRLM in a homogeneous group of patients stratified according to internationally validated prognostic risk scores and to assess the differences in long-term oncologic outcomes.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Study design

This is a multicentre retrospective observational study. Patients who underwent liver resection for colorectal metastases between January 2010 and December 2015 were included. The study was approved by the ethical committee with the registry number 3674, and it was performed following

the STROBE recommendation (16). The research protocol was registered at <https://clinicaltrials.gov/> with the identifier NCT04513457.

An invitation to participate in this study was sent via the Spanish Association of Surgery (Asociación Española de Cirujanos, [AEC]), and it was afterwards extended to international centres. In order to qualify to participate in the study, centres had to be specialised hepatobiliary surgery units. Inclusion criteria were: (a) patients older than 18 years with resectable liver metastases of histologically confirmed primary colorectal carcinoma and (b) liver resection performed in specialised liver surgery units. Exclusion criteria were patients with R2 resections.

Management

All patients diagnosed with colorectal cancer were assessed in specialised regional/local multidisciplinary tumour board meetings, and the treatment strategy was decided according to each centre protocol. Preoperative evaluation was performed by triphasic computed tomography (CT) of the chest, abdomen and pelvis in all patients and usually complemented with magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) of the liver. A PET scan was additionally indicated in patients with a suspicion/high risk of extrahepatic disease. Resectability was defined as the possibility to achieve complete macroscopic resection with an estimated future remnant liver volume of at least 25–30%. Patients with a marginal future liver remnant were considered for two-stage procedures when necessary. Patients with extrahepatic disease were included only if this was considered resectable. The objective of the resection was to achieve a microscopically complete resection. The pedicle clamping technique was commonly used during transection. Follow-up was carried out with thoracoabdominal CT and blood tests performed every three to six months for the first two years after hepatectomy and then every six months for the first five years. Follow-up was terminated after ten years in patients with no evidence of disease. Recurrence was defined as documentation of colorectal metastatic disease either radiologically or by biopsy, after the liver resection.

Our database included the following variables: age, sex, and body mass index (BMI); anaesthetic risk score (American Society of Anaesthesiologists [ASA] classification) (17); comorbidities; data related to the colorectal cancer (CRC) (date of diagnosis, interval between CRC and CRLM diagnosis, TNM staging); laboratory and radiological findings (carcinoembryonic antigen [CEA], number of CRLMs, size and location of the largest lesion, as determined by preoperative imaging); data on perioperative CTx (type of treatment, number of cycles); operative details (approach, duration, type of resection, blood loss, Pringle manoeuvre time, operative length, intraoperative events); complications within the first 30 postoperative days according to the Clavien-Dindo classification (18) (including bleeding, bile leak, postoperative liver failure, reoperations and mortality); histopathological data (including resection

margin, tumour grade, biomarkers) and oncological outcome (including recurrence rate, recurrence-free survival [RFS] and overall survival [OS], **calculated after excluding perioperative deaths**).

The included patients were initially divided into two groups according to whether they received perioperative CTx or not. Then, they were stratified according to widely used prognostic risk scores for recurrence cited by the vast majority of the most recent consensus papers and clinical guidelines including the Clinical Risk Score (CRS) (19), the Tumour Burden Score (20) and the Genetic And Morphological Evaluation (GAME) score (21).

Statistical analysis

Descriptive data were expressed as counts and proportions for categorical variables; continuous variables were presented as mean with standard deviation (SD) if normally distributed. Non-normal variables were presented as median with interquartile ranges (IQR). Univariable comparisons of patient characteristics and peri-intervention details between patients undergoing perioperative CTx and surgery alone for CRLM were performed using the Mann-Whitney U test, Pearson's χ^2 test, and Cox regression for continuous, categorical, and time-to-event variables, respectively. **A bivariable Cox regression analysis was used to identify predictors of decrease RFS and OS. Variables significant on the bivariable analysis were subsequently included in a multivariable cox regression model.**

Propensity score matching (PSM) was performed to minimise confounding. Prior to propensity score analyses, missing data were multiply imputed (M=50) using multivariable chained equations (22) with the following specifications: an ordinal logistic model for ordered factor variables (e.g. tumour grade, GAME score), a Poisson regression model for count variables (e.g. number of lesions), predictive mean matching with 10 k-nearest neighbours for continuous variables (e.g. size of the largest lesion, bilirubin), and augmented logistic regression for binary variables (e.g. sex, KRAS mutational status) (23-25). **In order to assess the randomness of the missing data, Little's test for missing completely at random (MCAR) was performed before imputation.**

Propensity score models were developed using logistic regression modelling after multiple imputation, and several models were developed and compared based on discrimination and calibration. The final model consisted of the following covariates: age, sex, ASA classification, comorbidities, bilirubin, albumin, creatinine and CEA levels, the T and N stage of colorectal cancer, interval time between primary tumour resection and diagnosis of CRLM, the size and number of liver metastases, previous liver resection, the type and extent of resection, concomitant ablation procedures, the tumour grade, and KRAS mutational status. PSM was performed using a 1:1 greedy matching algorithm without replacement and a caliper of 0.25*standard deviations of the linear predictor. Comparisons in the matched cohort took into account stratification by matched pairs; hence

Wilcoxon signed-rank test, McNemar's χ^2 test, and random effects gamma frailty Cox models were used for continuous, categorical, and time-to-event variables, respectively.

Statistical analyses were performed in Stata version 16.0 (StataCorp) (26), and nominal two-sided $p < 0.05$ were considered to indicate statistical significance.

RESULTS:

Assessment of baseline characteristics, surgical and oncological outcome

We included 967 patients (Table 1): 188 (19.5%) underwent surgery alone, while 779 (80.5%) received perioperative CTx; 594 (76.4%) in the form of neoadjuvant CTx, 508 (66.2%) in the form of adjuvant CTx and 323 (33.4%) in the form of combined perioperative CTx (Tables 1 and 2). Of nine centres recruiting patients, three provided less than 20 cases per year, four between 20 and 50 and one more than 50 cases per year.

Perioperative CTx was based mainly on a combination of two drugs for a total minimum duration of three months (six cycles). FOLFOX (folinic acid, 5-FU and oxaliplatin) was given to 46.5% of patients receiving CTx. Other regimens were a combination of FOLFIRI (folinic acid, 5-FU and irinotecan) given to 18.2% of patients receiving CTx; XELOX (capecitabine and oxaliplatin) given to 14.5%; LV5FU2 (leucovorin and 5-FU) given to 6.7%; UFT (uracil and tegafur) given to 3.8%. Eighty-five percent of patients receiving CTx were given at least six cycles.

As shown in table 2, 280 patients (29.1%) underwent major liver resection. During the postoperative period 130 patients (13.6%) presented complications \geq Clavien-Dindo IIIA, and there were 24 deaths at 90 days (2.5%). Median follow-up was 68 months: 665 patients (70.9%) had disease recurrence; median OS was 51 months (IQR 43–56 months) (Fig. 1A), while median RFS was 15 months (IQR 14–16 months) (Fig. 1B).

Comparison of surgery versus surgery with CTx

The unmatched cohort comparison between perioperative CTx and surgery alone demonstrated that patients receiving systemic treatment were younger (64 vs 70 years, $p > 0.001$) with more advanced primary colorectal disease, more synchronous (57.6% vs 21.2%, $p > 0.001$), multifocal (57.9% vs 28.3%, $p > 0.001$), bilobar CRLM (38.8% vs 15.0%, $p = 0.001$) and with higher TBS and GAME scores (both $p > 0.001$) (Table 1). Furthermore, they more often underwent major liver resection (31.0% vs 20.9%, $p = 0.007$) or liver resections combined with ablation procedures (16.3% vs 6.3%, $p = 0.002$) with prolonged operative time (225 min vs 160 min, $p < 0.001$; Table 2). No differences in RFS and OS were seen in this unmatched cohort (Fig. 1A–1B).

The bivariable analysis showed that the N stage (HR 1.201, 95%CI 1.090-1.323, $p<0.001$), the number of lesions (HR 1.029, 95%CI 1.015-1.044, $p<0.001$), the size of the biggest lesion (HR 1.002, 95%CI 1.001-1.003, $p<0.001$), the radicality of CRLM resection (HR 1.252, 95%CI 1.063-1.474, $p=0.007$), mutations in KRAS and BRAF (HR 1.609, 95%CI 1.056-2.095, $p=0.023$) and the absence of perioperative CTx (HR 0.594, 95%CI 0.449-0.787, $p<0.001$) were associated with decreased RFS (Table 3). Additionally, the age (HR 1.011, 95%CI 1.002-1.019, $p=0.009$), a short disease-free survival from the colorectal resection (HR 0.992, 95%CI 0.985-0.998, $p=0.015$), the N stage (HR 1.132, 95%CI 1.012-1.265, $p=0.029$), major liver resections (HR 1.213, 95%CI 1.003-1.467, $p=0.046$), postoperative complications \geq Clavien-Dindo IIIA (HR 1.445, 95%CI 1.004-2.081, $p=0.047$), the radicality of CRLM resection (HR 1.265, 95%CI 1.046- 1.529, $p=0.015$), mutations in KRAS and BRAF (HR 1.488, 95%CI 1.056-2.095, $p=0.023$) and perioperative CTx (HR 0.568, 95%CI 0.412-0.782, $p=0.001$) were associated with decreased OS. However, on the multivariable analysis exclusively the radicality of CRLM resection (HR 1.626, 95%CI 1.020-2.593, $p=0.041$) resulted an independent predictor of decreased RFS and perioperative CTx resulted an independent predictor of decreased both RFS and OS (HR 0.535, 95%CI 0.320-0.760, $p=0.001$ and HR 0.644, 95%CI 0.426-0.974, $p=0.037$, respectively).

The PSM model exhibited good discrimination (AUC=0.8062, bootstrapped 95% CI: 0.7702–0.8423) and calibration ($P=0.3899$ from Hosmer-Lemeshow test with 10 deciles) (Supplementary Figures S1, S2). Log odds of the propensity score and baseline covariates were well balanced after matching (Table 4 and supplementary Figures S3, S4). After PSM, patients who had perioperative CTx presented a longer operative time (210 vs 160 min, $p<0.001$) and an increased number of postoperative episodes of haemorrhage (4.7% vs 0.6%, $p=0.013$) without differences in other post-operative outcomes or histopathological findings (Table 5). However, patients with perioperative CTx presented significantly prolonged OS in comparison with surgery alone (median OS 82.8 months vs 52.5 months, $p=0.017$) (Fig. 1C). The CTx group presented also a slightly longer RFS but this difference was not statistically significant (Fig. 1D).

Comparison of surgery versus surgery with CTx according to prognostic risk factors and CRS and GAME scores

Patients included in the PSM were then stratified according to prognostic risk factors and established risk scores (Fig. 2). Perioperative CTx confirmed the benefit on OS in patients with a CRS (HR 0.66, 95% CI 0.47 – 0.94, $p=0.022$) and a TBS score up to 2 (HR 0.67, 95% CI 0.48 – 0.94, $p=0.020$) but not for higher CRS or TBS scores (Fig. 3,4). The same effect was confirmed in patients with a GAME score of 0 or 1 (HR 0.62, 95% CI 0.48 – 0.87, $p=0.006$) but not in patients with higher GAME values (Fig. 5).

DISCUSSION:

While resection is firmly established as the most effective treatment for resectable CRLM (27), it is unclear whether perioperative CTx has an impact on long-term survival, particularly in patients with a low risk of disease recurrence. By using PSM to emulate the randomization process and adjust the study and control group for confounding (28, 29), this study showed that patients undergoing perioperative CTx presented prolonged OS in up-front resectable CRLM, especially in those patients with a low risk of recurrence.

In an unmatched cohort comparison, the perioperative CTx group did not show prolonged survival despite having a much higher risk disease profile, implying that the poorer prognosis expected in this cohort was to some degree offset by the addition of perioperative chemotherapy. This was confirmed by the PSM analysis that demonstrated a clear improvement in OS when perioperative CTx was added to surgery alone. Importantly, subgroup analysis confirmed the potential benefit of perioperative CTx in patients with low risk of recurrence with an increase in median OS from 58 to 72 months. Although we could not prove the benefit of perioperative CTx in high-risk patients, this finding is likely limited by the much smaller sample population and event rate in this group. Indeed, the small number of high-risk patients included in this dataset suggest that oncological selection for surgery by local teams may already be taking place, either based on formal or informal risk assessment. Only 9.4% of the PSM cohort was based on high-risk patients (n=33). We estimated that 176 subjects with high-risk CRLM would be needed to achieve a 0.80 statistical power, at 0.05 significance level, to detect a HR of 0.65, comparable to the HR provided by the low risk subgroup analysis. Additionally, the PSM itself, with its matching process could have influenced a selection of patients in the perioperative CTx group that despite presenting a high-risk of recurrence according to the risk scores, presented less aggressive characteristics. The small group of 33 high-risk patients was based on only 6 patients with a CRS > 3 or a 4 patients GAME score > 2. Patients in the surgery alone group, even if included in the high-category presented lower scores than patients in the perioperative CTx group and the matching process could have favoured an exclusion of those patients with higher scores. Therefore, both the small number of cases and the exclusion of patients with more aggressive characteristics could have influenced the lack of significant differences in high-risk patients.

Several retrospective series have suggested prolonged survival in resected CRLM treated with concomitant systemic CTx (10-12). In a population-based retrospective study from Germany, Hackl et al. (30) assessed 1,426 patients with CRLM and a follow-up of more than ten years. Multivariable analysis showed significantly improved OS in patients with perioperative CTx. Another recent

retrospective study by Wang et al. (31) assessed the benefit of adjuvant CTx demonstrating significantly improved RFS and OS in 163 patients with CRLM. Nevertheless, there is a paucity of high-quality studies on long-term outcomes to confirm these results, as randomised studies investigating perioperative chemotherapy versus surgery alone have either failed due to recruitment issues (13-15) or have not been able to prove a long-term survival benefit.

Despite its retrospective nature, this study represents an attempt to emulate the randomisation process, with the PSM analysis aiming to homogenise study groups, thus limiting confounding.

Furthermore, it is based on a large contemporary multicentric cohort of patients operated on during the last decade, treated with modern regimens of CTx and with a median follow-up of more than five years. As such, it offers a real-world assessment of current clinical practice. Furthermore, multivariable analysis suggested that post-operative complications (\geq Dindo Clavien IIIa) were associated with a worse outcome. This may possibly be caused by a delay or lack of fitness for adjuvant CTx, however, the current dataset was not able to provide this level of data.

Resectable CRLM can include a wide spectrum of disease, ranging from cases with isolated metachronous liver metastases to synchronous bilobar liver metastases with concomitant extrahepatic disease. A number of scoring systems have been published over the years that stratify patients into high- and low-risk groups based on clinicopathologic variables related to the primary and metastatic disease (19, 21, 32, 33). The CRS proposed by Fong et al. (19) has been used for about two decades to predict patients' prognoses. More recently, Margonis et al. proposed the GAME score (21) that combined clinicopathological factors with genetic and morphological parameters. They demonstrated that the GAME score was able to outperform the CRS in predicting outcome. A retrospective series from Ayez et al. subsequently (34) analysed the results of 363 patients with hepatic resection for CRLM undergoing liver resection with or without neoadjuvant CTx and stratified them according to the CRS. While in the low CRS group there was no significant difference in median OS between patients with and without CTx (65 months vs. 54 months, $p=0.31$), the high CRS group presented a significant increase in OS (46 months vs. 33 months, $p=0.004$). For these reasons, they concluded that patients with a high CRS could benefit from neoadjuvant CTx.

There are several limitations to our series. Despite our efforts to generate a homogeneous group of patients through a PSM analysis and stratifying patients according to validated risk scores, the study is still based on retrospective data coming from an international group of centres, and this can increase the possibility of potential selection bias. Similarly, there was still a certain degree of heterogeneity regarding the number and type of perioperative CTx. Furthermore, it must be considered that, there is not a universally accepted definition of borderline resectable borderline CRLM, that might slightly differ between centres included in our study. Accordingly, we have tried to apply the lowest common

denominator by defining resectability only by a future liver remnant of 25-30%, a definition that is commonly accepted by many experienced hepatobiliary surgeons. This analysis included only patients with resected CRLM and did not consider those ones who had upfront CTx, progressed, and were not operated on. The exclusion of this group of patients with more advanced CRLM is another reason that could explain the lack of survival benefit for perioperative CTx in the higher risk cohort.

In conclusion, this study shows that when homogeneous groups of patients are compared, the use of modern CTx agents was associated with increased OS in resectable CRLM, especially in those with low risk for recurrence. Consequently, it supports current clinical guidelines and consensus papers (6-8).

Nevertheless, large-scale, adequately powered level I studies assessing homogeneous patients stratified according to modern risk scores are still needed to confirm the real benefits of perioperative CTx in patients with CRLM. The ongoing CHARISMA trial, investigating whether neoadjuvant XELOX improves survival in high-risk CRLM patients, should provide more insight on this topic (35).

Fig. 1: OS and RFS in the overall cohort (A-B) and after propensity score matching (C-D).

Fig. 2: Differences in OS of the PSM cohort stratified according to CRS, TBS and GAME scores.

Fig. 3: OS curves of the PSM cohort stratified according to CRS. Figure A shows survival of patients with a CRS ≤ 2 ; while B relates to patients with a CRS > 2 . Number of patients at risk at t=0 may differ from total sample size due to missing data.

Fig. 4: OS curves of the PSM cohort stratified according to TBS. Figure A shows survival of patients with a TBS ≤ 2 ; while B relates to patients with a TBS > 2 .

Fig. 5: OS curves of the PSM cohort stratified according to GAME score. Figure A shows survival of patients with a GAME score of 1; while B relates to patients with a GAME score > 1 .

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Perioperative chemotherapy versus surgery alone for resectable colorectal liver metastases: an international multicentre propensity score matched analysis on long-term outcomes according to established prognostic risk scores

ABSTRACT

Background:

There is still uncertainty regarding the role of perioperative chemotherapy (CTx) in patients with resectable colorectal liver metastases (CRLM), especially in those with a low-risk of recurrence.

Methods:

Multicentre retrospective analysis of patients with CRLM undergoing liver resection between 2010-2015. Patients were divided into two groups according to whether they received perioperative CTx or not and were compared using propensity score matching (PSM) analysis. Then, they were stratified according to prognostic risk scores, including: Clinical Risk Score (CRS), Tumour Burden Score (TBS) and Genetic And Morphological Evaluation (GAME) score.

Results:

The study included 967 patients with a median follow-up of 68 months. After PSM analysis, patients with perioperative CTx presented prolonged overall survival (OS) in comparison with the surgery alone group (82.8 vs 52.5 months, $p=0.017$). On multivariable analysis perioperative CTx was an independent predictor of increased OS (HR 0.705, 95%CI 0.705-0.516, $p=0.029$).

The benefits of perioperative CTx on survival were confirmed in patients with CRS and TBS scores ≤ 2 ($p=0.022$ and $p=0.020$, respectively) and in patients with a GAME score ≤ 1 ($p=0.006$).

Conclusion: Perioperative CTx demonstrated an increase in OS in patients with CRLM. Patients with a low-risk of recurrence seem to benefit from systemic treatment.

BACKGROUND:

Colorectal liver metastases (CRLM) is one of the leading causes of death from cancer (1) with a recurrence rate of 50–75% and a 5-year overall survival rate of about 50% in resected patients (2, 3). Liver resection represents the gold standard of treatment for resectable CRLM. While the role of chemotherapy (CTx) in unresectable or borderline resectable CRLM is well established, with the aim of decreasing the patients' tumour burden and achieving a safe liver resection, there is still debate regarding the role of perioperative CTx in the context of resectable CRLM (4, 5).

In clinical practice, the combination of surgery and CTx is increasingly accepted as treatment for resectable CRLM (6-8). However, there is a paucity of level I evidence studies (9) assessing the long-term outcomes of resected CRLM that support these recommendations. Despite several retrospective series suggesting a potential survival benefit for patients with CRLM who underwent liver resection in combination with CTx (10-12), randomised clinical trials (RCT) have not confirmed these findings. A pooled analysis of two phase III RCT was not able to prove survival advantages in favour of adjuvant CTx (13). Similarly, although the first publication of the European Organization for Research and Treatment of Cancer (EORTC) 40983 (EPOC) trial reported improved progression-free survival in patients with resectable CRLM receiving perioperative CTx compared to surgery alone, this did not translate into increased overall survival in the long-term analysis (14, 15). This uncertainty regarding CRLM management may partly be due to the fact that these studies were not well powered to detect minor differences in long-term outcomes, and they often involved a very heterogeneous group of patients not stratified according to the prognostic factors for risk of recurrence. Despite the lack of level I evidence (9), perioperative CTx is usually recommended in patients with CRLM, especially in those with a high risk of recurrence, but there is still significant uncertainty regarding its role in patients with a low risk of recurrence (6-8).

The aim of this study is to evaluate the role of perioperative CTx for CRLM in a homogeneous group of patients stratified according to internationally validated prognostic risk scores and to assess the differences in long-term oncologic outcomes.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Study design

This is a multicentre retrospective observational study. Patients who underwent liver resection for colorectal metastases between January 2010 and December 2015 were included. The study was approved by the ethical committee with the registry number 3674, and it was performed following

the STROBE recommendation (16). The research protocol was registered at <https://clinicaltrials.gov/> with the identifier NCT04513457.

An invitation to participate in this study was sent via the Spanish Association of Surgery (Asociación Española de Cirujanos, [AEC]), and it was afterwards extended to international centres. In order to qualify to participate in the study, centres had to be specialised hepatobiliary surgery units. Inclusion criteria were: (a) patients older than 18 years with resectable liver metastases of histologically confirmed primary colorectal carcinoma and (b) liver resection performed in specialised liver surgery units. Exclusion criteria were patients with R2 resections.

Management

All patients diagnosed with colorectal cancer were assessed in specialised regional/local multidisciplinary tumour board meetings, and the treatment strategy was decided according to each centre protocol. Preoperative evaluation was performed by triphasic computed tomography (CT) of the chest, abdomen and pelvis in all patients and usually complemented with magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) of the liver. A PET scan was additionally indicated in patients with a suspicion/high risk of extrahepatic disease. Resectability was defined as the possibility to achieve complete macroscopic resection with an estimated future remnant liver volume of at least 25–30%. Patients with a marginal future liver remnant were considered for two-stage procedures when necessary. Patients with extrahepatic disease were included only if this was considered resectable. The objective of the resection was to achieve a microscopically complete resection. The pedicle clamping technique was commonly used during transection. Follow-up was carried out with thoracoabdominal CT and blood tests performed every three to six months for the first two years after hepatectomy and then every six months for the first five years. Follow-up was terminated after ten years in patients with no evidence of disease. Recurrence was defined as documentation of colorectal metastatic disease either radiologically or by biopsy, after the liver resection.

Our database included the following variables: age, sex, and body mass index (BMI); anaesthetic risk score (American Society of Anaesthesiologists [ASA] classification) (17); comorbidities; data related to the colorectal cancer (CRC) (date of diagnosis, interval between CRC and CRLM diagnosis, TNM staging); laboratory and radiological findings (carcinoembryonic antigen [CEA], number of CRLMs, size and location of the largest lesion, as determined by preoperative imaging; data on perioperative CTx (type of treatment, number of cycles); operative details (approach, duration, type of resection, blood loss, Pringle manoeuvre time, operative length, intraoperative events); complications within the first 30 postoperative days according to the Clavien-Dindo classification (18) (including bleeding, bile leak, postoperative liver failure, reoperations and mortality); histopathological data (including resection

margin, tumour grade, biomarkers) and oncological outcome (including recurrence rate, recurrence-free survival [RFS] and overall survival [OS], calculated after excluding perioperative deaths).

The included patients were initially divided into two groups according to whether they received perioperative CTx or not. Then, they were stratified according to widely used prognostic risk scores for recurrence cited by the vast majority of the most recent consensus papers and clinical guidelines including the Clinical Risk Score (CRS) (19), the Tumour Burden Score (20) and the Genetic And Morphological Evaluation (GAME) score (21).

Statistical analysis

Descriptive data were expressed as counts and proportions for categorical variables; continuous variables were presented as mean with standard deviation (SD) if normally distributed. Non-normal variables were presented as median with interquartile ranges (IQR). Univariable comparisons of patient characteristics and peri-intervention details between patients undergoing perioperative CTx and surgery alone for CRLM were performed using the Mann-Whitney U test, Pearson's χ^2 test, and Cox regression for continuous, categorical, and time-to-event variables, respectively. A bivariable Cox regression analysis was used to identify predictors of decrease RFS and OS. Variables significant on the bivariable analysis were subsequently included in a multivariable cox regression model.

Propensity score matching (PSM) was performed to minimise confounding. Prior to propensity score analyses, missing data were multiply imputed (M=50) using multivariable chained equations (22) with the following specifications: an ordinal logistic model for ordered factor variables (e.g. tumour grade, GAME score), a Poisson regression model for count variables (e.g. number of lesions), predictive mean matching with 10 k-nearest neighbours for continuous variables (e.g. size of the largest lesion, bilirubin), and augmented logistic regression for binary variables (e.g. sex, KRAS mutational status) (23-25). In order to assess the randomness of the missing data, Little's test for missing completely at random (MCAR) was performed before imputation.

Propensity score models were developed using logistic regression modelling after multiple imputation, and several models were developed and compared based on discrimination and calibration. The final model consisted of the following covariates: age, sex, ASA classification, comorbidities, bilirubin, albumin, creatinine and CEA levels, the T and N stage of colorectal cancer, interval time between primary tumour resection and diagnosis of CRLM, the size and number of liver metastases, previous liver resection, the type and extent of resection, concomitant ablation procedures, the tumour grade, and KRAS mutational status. PSM was performed using a 1:1 greedy matching algorithm without replacement and a caliper of 0.25*standard deviations of the linear predictor. Comparisons in the matched cohort took into account stratification by matched pairs; hence

Wilcoxon signed-rank test, McNemar's χ^2 test, and random effects gamma frailty Cox models were used for continuous, categorical, and time-to-event variables, respectively.

Statistical analyses were performed in Stata version 16.0 (StataCorp) (26), and nominal two-sided $p < 0.05$ were considered to indicate statistical significance.

RESULTS:

Assessment of baseline characteristics, surgical and oncological outcome

We included 967 patients (Table 1): 188 (19.5%) underwent surgery alone, while 779 (80.5%) received perioperative CTx; 594 (76.4%) in the form of neoadjuvant CTx, 508 (66.2%) in the form of adjuvant CTx and 323 (33.4%) in the form of combined perioperative CTx (Tables 1 and 2). Of nine centres recruiting patients, three provided less than 20 cases per year, four between 20 and 50 and one more than 50 cases per year.

Perioperative CTx was based mainly on a combination of two drugs for a total minimum duration of three months (six cycles). FOLFOX (folinic acid, 5-FU and oxaliplatin) was given to 46.5% of patients receiving CTx. Other regimens were a combination of FOLFIRI (folinic acid, 5-FU and irinotecan) given to 18.2% of patients receiving CTx; XELOX (capecitabine and oxaliplatin) given to 14.5%; LV5FU2 (leucovorin and 5-FU) given to 6.7%; UFT (uracil and tegafur) given to 3.8%. Eighty-five percent of patients receiving CTx were given at least six cycles.

As shown in table 2, 280 patients (29.1%) underwent major liver resection. During the postoperative period 130 patients (13.6%) presented complications \geq Clavien-Dindo IIIA, and there were 24 deaths at 90 days (2.5%). Median follow-up was 68 months: 665 patients (70.9%) had disease recurrence; median OS was 51 months (IQR 43–56 months) (Fig. 1A), while median RFS was 15 months (IQR 14–16 months) (Fig. 1B).

Comparison of surgery versus surgery with CTx

The unmatched cohort comparison between perioperative CTx and surgery alone demonstrated that patients receiving systemic treatment were younger (64 vs 70 years, $p > 0.001$) with more advanced primary colorectal disease, more synchronous (57.6% vs 21.2%, $p > 0.001$), multifocal (57.9% vs 28.3%, $p > 0.001$), bilobar CRLM (38.8% vs 15.0%, $p = 0.001$) and with higher TBS and GAME scores (both $p > 0.001$) (Table 1). Furthermore, they more often underwent major liver resection (31.0% vs 20.9%, $p = 0.007$) or liver resections combined with ablation procedures (16.3% vs 6.3%, $p = 0.002$) with prolonged operative time (225 min vs 160 min, $p < 0.001$; Table 2). No differences in RFS and OS were seen in this unmatched cohort (Fig. 1A–1B).

The bivariable analysis showed that the N stage (HR 1.201, 95%CI 1.090-1.323, $p<0.001$), the number of lesions (HR 1.029, 95%CI 1.015-1.044, $p<0.001$), the size of the biggest lesion (HR 1.002, 95%CI 1.001-1.003, $p<0.001$), the radicality of CRLM resection (HR 1.252, 95%CI 1.063-1.474, $p=0.007$), mutations in KRAS and BRAF (HR 1.609, 95%CI 1.056-2.095, $p=0.023$) and the absence of perioperative CTx (HR 0.594, 95%CI 0.449-0.787, $p<0.001$) were associated with decreased RFS (Table 3). Additionally, the age (HR 1.011, 95%CI 1.002-1.019, $p=0.009$), a short disease-free survival from the colorectal resection (HR 0.992, 95%CI 0.985-0.998, $p=0.015$), the N stage (HR 1.132, 95%CI 1.012-1.265, $p=0.029$), major liver resections (HR 1.213, 95%CI 1.003-1.467, $p=0.046$), postoperative complications \geq Clavien-Dindo IIIA (HR 1.445, 95%CI 1.004-2.081, $p=0.047$), the radicality of CRLM resection (HR 1.265, 95%CI 1.046- 1.529, $p=0.015$), mutations in KRAS and BRAF (HR 1.488, 95%CI 1.056-2.095, $p=0.023$) and perioperative CTx (HR 0.568, 95%CI 0.412-0.782, $p=0.001$) were associated with decreased OS. However, on the multivariable analysis exclusively the radicality of CRLM resection (HR 1.626, 95%CI 1.020-2.593, $p=0.041$) resulted an independent predictor of decreased RFS and perioperative CTx resulted an independent predictor of decreased both RFS and OS (HR 0.535, 95%CI 0.320-0.760, $p=0.001$ and HR 0.644, 95%CI 0.426-0.974, $p=0.037$, respectively).

The PSM model exhibited good discrimination (AUC=0.8062, bootstrapped 95% CI: 0.7702–0.8423) and calibration ($P=0.3899$ from Hosmer-Lemeshow test with 10 deciles) (Supplementary Figures S1, S2). Log odds of the propensity score and baseline covariates were well balanced after matching (Table 4 and supplementary Figures S3, S4). After PSM, patients who had perioperative CTx presented a longer operative time (210 vs 160 min, $p<0.001$) and an increased number of postoperative episodes of haemorrhage (4.7% vs 0.6%, $p=0.013$) without differences in other post-operative outcomes or histopathological findings (Table 5). However, patients with perioperative CTx presented significantly prolonged OS in comparison with surgery alone (median OS 82.8 months vs 52.5 months, $p=0.017$) (Fig. 1C). The CTx group presented also a slightly longer RFS but this difference was not statistically significant (Fig. 1D).

Comparison of surgery versus surgery with CTx according to prognostic risk factors and CRS and GAME scores

Patients included in the PSM were then stratified according to prognostic risk factors and established risk scores (Fig. 2). Perioperative CTx confirmed the benefit on OS in patients with a CRS (HR 0.66, 95% CI 0.47 – 0.94, $p=0.022$) and a TBS score up to 2 (HR 0.67, 95% CI 0.48 – 0.94, $p=0.020$) but not for higher CRS or TBS scores (Fig. 3,4). The same effect was confirmed in patients with a GAME score of 0 or 1 (HR 0.62, 95% CI 0.48 – 0.87, $p=0.006$) but not in patients with higher GAME values (Fig. 5).

DISCUSSION:

While resection is firmly established as the most effective treatment for resectable CRLM (27), it is unclear whether perioperative CTx has an impact on long-term survival, particularly in patients with a low risk of disease recurrence. By using PSM to emulate the randomization process and adjust the study and control group for confounding (28, 29), this study showed that patients undergoing perioperative CTx presented prolonged OS in up-front resectable CRLM, especially in those patients with a low risk of recurrence.

In an unmatched cohort comparison, the perioperative CTx group did not show prolonged survival despite having a much higher risk disease profile, implying that the poorer prognosis expected in this cohort was to some degree offset by the addition of perioperative chemotherapy. This was confirmed by the PSM analysis that demonstrated a clear improvement in OS when perioperative CTx was added to surgery alone. Importantly, subgroup analysis confirmed the potential benefit of perioperative CTx in patients with low risk of recurrence with an increase in median OS from 58 to 72 months. Although we could not prove the benefit of perioperative CTx in high-risk patients, this finding is likely limited by the much smaller sample population and event rate in this group. Indeed, the small number of high-risk patients included in this dataset suggest that oncological selection for surgery by local teams may already be taking place, either based on formal or informal risk assessment. Only 9.4% of the PSM cohort was based on high-risk patients (n=33). We estimated that 176 subjects with high-risk CRLM would be needed to achieve a 0.80 statistical power, at 0.05 significance level, to detect a HR of 0.65, comparable to the HR provided by the low risk subgroup analysis. Additionally, the PSM itself, with its matching process could have influenced a selection of patients in the perioperative CTx group that despite presenting a high-risk of recurrence according to the risk scores, presented less aggressive characteristics. The small group of 33 high-risk patients was based on only 6 patients with a CRS > 3 or a 4 patients GAME score > 2. Patients in the surgery alone group, even if included in the high-category presented lower scores than patients in the perioperative CTx group and the matching process could have favoured an exclusion of those patients with higher scores. Therefore, both the small number of cases and the exclusion of patients with more aggressive characteristics could have influenced the lack of significant differences in high-risk patients.

Several retrospective series have suggested prolonged survival in resected CRLM treated with concomitant systemic CTx (10-12). In a population-based retrospective study from Germany, Hackl et al. (30) assessed 1,426 patients with CRLM and a follow-up of more than ten years. Multivariable analysis showed significantly improved OS in patients with perioperative CTx. Another recent

retrospective study by Wang et al. (31) assessed the benefit of adjuvant CTx demonstrating significantly improved RFS and OS in 163 patients with CRLM. Nevertheless, there is a paucity of high-quality studies on long-term outcomes to confirm these results, as randomised studies investigating perioperative chemotherapy versus surgery alone have either failed due to recruitment issues (13-15) or have not been able to prove a long-term survival benefit.

Despite its retrospective nature, this study represents an attempt to emulate the randomisation process, with the PSM analysis aiming to homogenise study groups, thus limiting confounding. Furthermore, it is based on a large contemporary multicentric cohort of patients operated on during the last decade, treated with modern regimens of CTx and with a median follow-up of more than five years. As such, it offers a real-world assessment of current clinical practice. Furthermore, multivariable analysis suggested that post-operative complications (\geq Dindo Clavien IIIa) were associated with a worse outcome. This may possibly be caused by a delay or lack of fitness for adjuvant CTx, however, the current dataset was not able to provide this level of data.

Resectable CRLM can include a wide spectrum of disease, ranging from cases with isolated metachronous liver metastases to synchronous bilobar liver metastases with concomitant extrahepatic disease. A number of scoring systems have been published over the years that stratify patients into high- and low-risk groups based on clinicopathologic variables related to the primary and metastatic disease (19, 21, 32, 33). The CRS proposed by Fong et al. (19) has been used for about two decades to predict patients' prognoses. More recently, Margonis et al. proposed the GAME score (21) that combined clinicopathological factors with genetic and morphological parameters. They demonstrated that the GAME score was able to outperform the CRS in predicting outcome. A retrospective series from Ayez et al. subsequently (34) analysed the results of 363 patients with hepatic resection for CRLM undergoing liver resection with or without neoadjuvant CTx and stratified them according to the CRS. While in the low CRS group there was no significant difference in median OS between patients with and without CTx (65 months vs. 54 months, $p=0.31$), the high CRS group presented a significant increase in OS (46 months vs. 33 months, $p=0.004$). For these reasons, they concluded that patients with a high CRS could benefit from neoadjuvant CTx.

There are several limitations to our series. Despite our efforts to generate a homogeneous group of patients through a PSM analysis and stratifying patients according to validated risk scores, the study is still based on retrospective data coming from an international group of centres, and this can increase the possibility of potential selection bias. Similarly, there was still a certain degree of heterogeneity regarding the number and type of perioperative CTx. Furthermore, it must be considered that, there is not a universally accepted definition of borderline resectable borderline CRLM, that might slightly differ between centres included in our study. Accordingly, we have tried to apply the lowest common

denominator by defining resectability only by a future liver remnant of 25-30%, a definition that is commonly accepted by many experienced hepatobiliary surgeons. This analysis included only patients with resected CRLM and did not consider those ones who had upfront CTx, progressed, and were not operated on. The exclusion of this group of patients with more advanced CRLM is another reason that could explain the lack of survival benefit for perioperative CTx in the higher risk cohort.

In conclusion, this study shows that when homogeneous groups of patients are compared, the use of modern CTx agents was associated with increased OS in resectable CRLM, especially in those with low risk for recurrence. Consequently, it supports current clinical guidelines and consensus papers (6-8). Nevertheless, large-scale, adequately powered level I studies assessing homogeneous patients stratified according to modern risk scores are still needed to confirm the real benefits of perioperative CTx in patients with CRLM. The ongoing CHARISMA trial, investigating whether neoadjuvant XELOX improves survival in high-risk CRLM patients, should provide more insight on this topic (35).

Fig. 1: OS and RFS in the overall cohort (A-B) and after propensity score matching (C-D).

Fig. 2: Differences in OS of the PSM cohort stratified according to CRS, TBS and GAME scores.

Fig. 3: OS curves of the PSM cohort stratified according to CRS. Figure A shows survival of patients with a CRS ≤ 2 ; while B relates to patients with a CRS > 2 . Number of patients at risk at t=0 may differ from total sample size due to missing data.

Fig. 4: OS curves of the PSM cohort stratified according to TBS. Figure A shows survival of patients with a TBS ≤ 2 ; while B relates to patients with a TBS > 2 .

Fig. 5: OS curves of the PSM cohort stratified according to GAME score. Figure A shows survival of patients with a GAME score of 1; while B relates to patients with a GAME score > 1 .

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No periop chemo	186	167	135	103	65	37	22	8	3	3	1
Periop chemo	764	683	574	420	311	230	162	90	47	14	7

No periop chemo	183	134	92	74	49	30	19	7	3	3	1
Periop chemo	756	506	369	273	217	164	115	63	33	12	5

No periop chemo	175	156	126	98	61	34	20	8	3	3	1
Periop chemo	175	155	130	105	86	69	51	32	15	2	0

No periop chemo	175	126	86	70	45	27	17	7	3	3	1
Periop chemo	175	124	92	75	66	53	40	26	11	3	1

Number at risk

No periop chemo	142	129	103	82	51	28	16	7	2	2	0
Periop chemo	141	126	108	91	75	62	46	30	15	2	0

Number at risk

No periop chemo	35	31	26	21	11	6	5	0	0	0	0
Periop chemo	32	28	23	17	15	11	8	3	1	0	0

Number at risk

	0	12	24	36	48	60	72	84	96	108	120
No periop chemo	142	129	103	82	51	28	16	7	2	2	0
Periop chemo	141	126	108	91	75	62	46	30	15	2	0

Number at risk

	0	12	24	36	48	60	72	84	96	108	120
No periop chemo	33	27	23	16	10	6	4	1	1	1	1
Periop chemo	34	29	22	14	11	7	5	2	0	0	0

Table 1 Comparison of baseline and preoperative characteristics in patients who underwent surgery only versus those who received peri-operative chemotherapy

	All patients (n=967)			
	Total (n=967)	Peri-op. chemotherapy (n=779)	Surgery alone (n=188)	p value
<i>Patient characteristics</i>				
Age (years), median (IQR)	65.0 (58.3 to 73.1)	64.0 (57.3 to 71.7)	70.2 (62.6 to 76.7)	<0.001
Male sex, n/total (%) [*]	623/967 (64.4%)	496/779 (63.7%)	127/188 (67.6%)	0.316
ASA classification, n/total (%) [*]				
ASA I-II	598/909 (65.8%)	486/732 (66.4%)	112/177 (63.3%)	0.435
ASA III-IV	311/909 (34.2%)	246/732 (33.6%)	65/177 (36.7%)	
<i>Disease characteristics</i>				
T stage 3 or 4, n/total (%) [*]	804/921 (87.3%)	656/739 (88.8%)	148/182 (81.3%)	0.010
N stage 1 or 2, n/total (%) [*]	561/928 (60.5%)	464/736 (62.2%)	97/182 (53.3%)	0.029
Synchronous CRLM, n/total (%) [*]	525/965 (54.4%)	448/778 (57.6%)	77/187 (41.2%)	<0.001
Total bilirubin, mg/dL, mean (SD)	0.7 (0.5 to 0.9)	0.6 (0.4 to 0.8)	0.9 (0.6 to 1.1)	<0.001
Albumin, mg/dL, median (IQR)	4.2 (4.0 to 4.4)	4.2 (4.0 to 4.4)	4.1 (3.9 to 4.3)	0.233
CEA, median (IQR)	7.2 (3.0 to 25.6)	7.0 (3.0 to 25.6)	8.0 (3.9 to 26.7)	0.193
Number of CRLM, n/total (%) [*]				
Solitary	436/938 (46.5%)	304/754 (40.3%)	132/184 (71.7%)	<0.001
Multifocal	502/938 (53.5%)	450/754 (59.7%)	52/184 (28.3%)	
Size of biggest CRLM, median (IQR)	30 (20 to 45)	30 (20 to 45)	32 (21 to 45)	0.077
Location of CRLM, n/total (%) [*]				
Unilobar	428/676 (63.3%)	377/616 (61.2%)	51/60 (85.0%)	0.001
Bilobar	248/676 (36.7%)	239/616 (38.8%)	9/60 (15.0%)	
GAME score, n/total (%) [*]				
Low-risk (0 or 1 points)	669/967 (69.2%)	515/779 (66.1%)	154/188 (81.9%)	<0.001
Medium- to high-risk (≥2 points)	298/967 (30.8%)	264/779 (33.9%)	34/188 (18.1%)	
Tumor burden score (TBS), n/total (%) [*]				
Category 0	676/967 (69.9%)	524/779 (67.3%)	152/188 (80.9%)	<0.001
Category 1 or 2	291/967 (30.1%)	255/779 (32.7%)	36/188 (19.1%)	
Clinical risk score, n/total (%) [*]				
Low-risk (CRS ≤2)	488/616 (79.2%)	402/513 (78.4%)	86/103 (83.5%)	0.231
High-risk (CRS ≥3)	128/616 (20.8%)	111/513 (21.6%)	17/103 (16.5%)	
<i>Neoadjuvant chemotherapy data</i>				
Neoadjuvant treatment, n/total (%) [*]	594/778 (76.4%)	594/778 (76.4%)	NA	NA
Patients receiving at least two chemotherapy drugs, n/total (%) [†]	563/588 (95.8%)	563/588 (95.8%)	NA	NA
Patients receiving biological agents, n/total (%) [†]	290/594(48.8%)	290/594(48.8%)	NA	NA
*Denominators may differ from total sample size due to missing data				
[†] Denominator only includes patients who received neoadjuvant systemic therapy				
NA: not applicable				

Table 2 Comparison of surgical characteristics and post-operative outcomes in patients who underwent surgery only versus those who received peri-operative chemotherapy

	All patients (n=967)			
	Total (n=967)	Peri-op. chemotherapy (n=779)	Surgery alone (n=188)	p value
<i>Surgical and perioperative data</i>				
Major resection, n/total (%)*	280/964 (29.1%)	241/777 (31.0%)	39/187 (20.9%)	0.007
Associated ablative procedures, n/total (%)*	130/896 (14.5%)	120/737 (16.3%)	10/159 (6.3%)	0.002
Pringle maneuver time, median (IQR) [†]	27 (18 to 41)	30 (18 to 42)	26 (18 to 40)	0.515
Blood loss (ml), median (IQR)	300 (100 to 747)	350 (140 to 800)	300 (100 to 500)	0.055
Operative time (min), median (IQR)	210 (135 to 285)	225 (150 to 290)	160 (105 to 225)	<0.001
<i>Post-operative complications</i>				
Complications ≥ Clavien-Dindo IIIA, n/total (%)*	130/958 (13.6%)	110/771 (14.3%)	20/187 (10.7%)	0.201
Bile leakage, n/total (%)*	51/939 (5.4%)	45/764 (5.9%)	6/175 (3.4%)	0.172
Haemorrhage, n/total (%)*	21/937 (2.2%)	19/764 (2.5%)	2/173 (1.2%)	0.249
Post-operative liver failure n/total (%)*	20/936 (2.1%)	18/762 (2.4%)	2/174 (1.2%)	0.283
Intrabdominal infection, n/total (%)*	89/951 (9.4%)	74/766 (9.7%)	15/185 (8.1%)	0.509
Reoperation, n/total (%)*	48/952 (5.0%)	39/770 (5.1%)	9/182 (5.0%)	0.890
90-days mortality n/total (%)*	24/953 (2.5%)	17/771 (2.2%)	7/182 (3.8%)	0.204
LOS, median (IQR)	6 (5 to 9)	6 (5 to 9)	6 (5 to 8)	0.186
<i>Histopathological findings</i>				
R0, n (%)	594/914 (65.0%)	482/732 (65.9%)	112/182 (61.5%)	0.278
Grade, n/total (%)				
Well/moderately-differentiated	495/542 (91.3%)	450/491 (91.7%)	45/51 (88.2%)	0.429
Poorly/un-differentiated	47/542 (8.7%)	41/491 (8.3%)	6/51 (11.8%)	
K-RAS positive, n/total (%)*	178/603 (29.5%)	162/550 (29.5%)	16/53 (30.2%)	0.911
<i>Adjuvant chemotherapy</i>				
Adjuvant treatment, n/total (%)*	508/768 (66.2%)	508/768 (66.2%)	NA	NA
Patients receiving at least two chemotherapy drugs, n/total (%) [‡]	409/467 (87.6%)	409/467 (87.6%)	NA	NA
Patients receiving biological agents, n/total (%) [‡]	182/474 (38.4%)	182/474 (38.4%)	NA	NA
<i>Oncological outcomes</i>				
Follow-up (months), median	68.4	72.0	58.6	NA
Recurrence-free survival (months)				
Median (IQR)	27.0 (9.5 to 74.6)	27.0 (8.9 to 74.6)	30.0 (12.0 to 80.0)	
1-year RFS (%)	69.6%	68.4%	74.8%	0.560
3-year RFS (%)	43.6%	43.3%	45.0%	
5-year RFS (%)	30.9%	31.6%	22.8%	
Overall survival (months)				
Median (IQR)	52.0 (28.0 to NR)	52.0 (28.1 to NR)	52.5 (22.6 to NR)	
1-year OS (%)	90.6%	91.0%	88.7%	0.391
3-year OS (%)	64.6%	65.1%	62.2%	
5-year OS (%)	45.9%	46.5%	42.9%	
10-year OS (%)	30.4%	30.5%	30.2%	

*Denominators may differ from total sample size due to missing data

[†]Pringle time was calculated only for patients for whom the Pringle maneuver was used

[‡] Denominator only includes patients who received adjuvant systemic therapy

NA: not applicable; NR: not reached

Table 3: Bivariable and multivariable analysis of factors related to recurrence free survival and overall survival from the unmatched cohort.

Recurrence Free Survival						
Variable	Bivariate analysis			Multivariate analysis		
	HR	95%CI	p-Value	HR	95%CI	p-Value
Age	.995	.988-1.002	0.225			
ASA classification	1.016	.908-1.138	0.771			
Disease-free survival from CR resection	.997	.991-1.002	0.305			
T stage colorectal cancer	1.053	.927-1.197	0.423			
N stage colorectal cancer	1.201	1.090-1.323	<0.001	---	---	---
Number of lesions	1.029	1.015-1.044	<0.001	---	---	---
Size of the biggest lesion	1.002	1.001-1.003	<0.001	---	---	---
Type of resection (major vs minor)	1.130	.955-1.337	0.154			
Complications \geq Clavien-Dindo IIIA	.742	.500-1.102	0.140			
Radicality CRLM resection (R1 vs R0)	1.252	1.063-1.474	0.007	---	---	---
KRAS/BRAF mutation*	1.609	1.056-2.095	0.023	---	---	---
Perioperative chemotherapy	.5946	.449-.787	<0.001	.535	.320-.760	0.001
Overall Survival						
Variable	Bivariate analysis			Multivariate analysis		
	HR	95%CI	p-Value	HR	95%CI	p-Value
Age	1.011	1.002-1.019	0.009	---	---	---
ASA classification	1.126	.986-1.285	0.079			
Disease-free survival from CR resection	.992	.985-.998	0.015	---	---	---
T stage colorectal cancer	1.135	.977- 1.319	0.097			
N stage colorectal cancer	1.132	1.012-1.265	0.029	---	---	---
Number of lesions	1.009	.996-1.023	0.164			
Size of the biggest lesion	1.000	.999-1.002	0.220			
Type of resection (major vs minor)	1.213	1.003-1.467	0.046	---	---	---
Complications \geq Clavien-Dindo IIIA	1.445	1.004-2.081	0.047	---	---	---
Radicality CRLM resection (R1 vs R0)	1.265	1.046- 1.529	0.015	1.626	1.020-2.593	0.041
KRAS/BRAF mutation*	1.488	1.056-2.095	0.023	---	---	---
Perioperative chemotherapy	0.568	.412-.782	0.001	.644	.426-.974	0.037

*This includes patients with mutated KRAS and/or BRAF

Table 4 Comparison of baseline and preoperative characteristics in patients who underwent surgery only versus those who received peri-operative chemotherapy after PSM analysis

	Propensity-score matched cohort (n=350)		
	Peri-op. chemotherapy (n=175)	Surgery alone (n=175)	p value
<i>Patient characteristics</i>			
Age (years), median (IQR)	67.9 (61.6 to 75.3)	70.7 (63.3 to 76.8)	0.167
Male sex, n/total (%) [*]	112/175 (64.0%)	118/175 (67.4%)	0.500
ASA classification, n/total (%) [*]			
ASA I-II	110/175 (62.9%)	110/175 (62.9%)	1.000
ASA III-IV	65/175 (37.1%)	65/175 (37.1%)	
<i>Disease characteristics</i>			
T stage 3 or 4, n/total (%) [*]	142/169 (84.0%)	142/173 (82.1%)	0.662
N stage 1 or 2, n/total (%) [*]	83/171 (48.5%)	90/173 (52.0%)	0.508
Synchronous CRLM, n/total (%) [*]	66/175 (37.7%)	76/174 (43.7%)	0.293
Total bilirubin, mg/dL, mean (SD)	0.6 (0.5 to 0.9)	0.8 (0.6 to 1.1)	0.576
Albumin, mg/dL, median (IQR)	4.2 (3.9 to 4.4)	4.1 (4.0 to 4.3)	0.513
CEA, median (IQR)	6.6 (3.0 to 15.0)	8.0 (4.0 to 29.4)	0.134
Number of CRLM, n/total (%) [*]			
Solitary	115/174 (66.1%)	122/171 (71.4%)	0.293
Multifocal	59/174 (28.7%)	49/171 (28.7%)	
Size of biggest CRLM, median (IQR)	30 (20 to 50)	33 (22 to 45)	0.529
Location of CRLM, n/total (%) [*]			
Unilobar	109/134 (81.3%)	42/51 (82.4%)	0.618
Bilobar	25/134 (18.7%)	9/51 (17.7%)	
GAME score, n/total (%) [*]			
Low-risk (0 or 1 points)	141/175 (80.6%)	142/175 (81.1%)	0.886
Medium- to high-risk (≥2 points)	34/175 (19.4%)	33/175 (18.9%)	
Tumor burden score (TBS), n/total (%) [*]			
Category 0	142/175 (81.1%)	140/175 (80.0%)	0.777
Category 1 or 2	33/175 (18.9%)	35/175 (20.0%)	
Clinical risk score, n/total (%) [*]			
Low-risk (CRS ≤2)	111/129 (86.1%)	82/97 (84.5%)	1.000
High-risk (CRS ≥3)	18/129 (13.9%)	15/97 (15.5%)	
<i>Neoadjuvant chemotherapy data</i>			
Neoadjuvant treatment, n/total (%) [*]	121/175 (69.1%)	NA	NA
Patients receiving at least two chemotherapy drugs, n/total (%) ^{††}	112/119 (94.1%)	NA	NA
Patients receiving biological agents, n/total (%) ^{††}	53/121 (43.8%)	NA	NA

^{*}Denominators may differ from total sample size due to missing data
^{††} Denominator only includes patients who received neoadjuvant systemic therapy
NA: not applicable

Table 5 Comparison of surgical characteristics and post-operative outcomes in patients who underwent surgery only versus those who received peri-operative chemotherapy after PSM analysis

	Propensity-score matched cohort (n=350)		
	Peri-op. chemotherapy (n=175)	Surgery alone (n=175)	p value
<i>Surgical and perioperative data</i>			
Major resection, n/total (%)*	31/175 (17.7%)	36/175 (20.6%)	0.467
Associated ablative procedures, n/total (%)*	10/167 (6.0%)	10/148 (6.8%)	1.000
Pringle maneuver time, median (IQR) [†]	30 (17 to 45)	25 (18 to 40)	0.287
Blood loss (ml), median (IQR)	350 (100 to 800)	300 (100 to 500)	0.446
Operative time (min), median (IQR)	210 (125 to 300)	160 (105 to 225)	<0.001
<i>Post-operative complications</i>			
Complications ≥ Clavien-Dindo IIIA, n/total (%)*	22/174 (12.6%)	20/175 (11.4%)	0.758
Bile leakage, n/total (%)*	10/172 (5.8%)	5/163 (3.1%)	0.292
Haemorrhage, n/total (%)*	8/172 (4.7%)	1/162 (0.6%)	0.013
Post-operative liver failure n/total (%)*	4/171 (2.3%)	2/163 (1.2%)	0.424
Intrabdominal infection, n/total (%)*	14/172 (8.1%)	13/173 (7.5%)	0.835
Reoperation, n/total (%)*	6/174 (3.5%)	8/171 (4.7%)	0.594
90-days mortality n/total (%)*	5/173 (2.9%)	7 (4.0%)	0.566
LOS, median (IQR)	6 (5 to 9)	6 (5 to 8)	0.164
<i>Histopathological findings</i>			
R0, n (%)	108/170 (63.5%)	105/172 (61.1%)	0.553
Grade, n/total (%)			
Well/moderately-differentiated	100/116 (86.2%)	41/47 (87.2%)	1.000
Poorly/un-differentiated	16/116 (13.8%)	6/47 (12.8%)	
K-RAS positive, n/total (%)*	28/120 (23.3%)	15/47 (31.9%)	0.763
<i>Adjuvant chemotherapy</i>			
Adjuvant treatment, n/total (%)*	119/173 (68.8%)	NA	NA
Patients receiving at least two chemotherapy drugs, n/total (%) [‡]	95/111 (85.6%)	NA	NA
Patients receiving biological agents, n/total (%) [‡]	30/118 (25.4%)	NA	NA
<i>Oncological outcomes</i>			
Follow-up (months), median	74.9	58.6	NA
Recurrence-free survival (months)			
Median (IQR)	35.6 (10.0 to 93.0)	31.0 (12.1 to 72.0)	
1-year RFS (%)	72.8%	75.8%	0.209
3-year RFS (%)	49.3%	45.2%	
5-year RFS (%)	39.4%	26.7%	
Overall survival (months)			
Median (IQR)	82.8 (33.5 to 105)	52.5 (22.6 to NR)	
1-year OS (%)	90.7%	89.6%	0.017
3-year OS (%)	71.6%	62.4%	
5-year OS (%)	57.9%	41.9%	

*Denominators may differ from total sample size due to missing data
[†]Pringle time was calculated only for patients for whom the Pringle maneuver was used
[‡] Denominator only includes patients who received adjuvant systemic therapy
NA: not applicable; NR: not reached

Table 1 Comparison of baseline and preoperative characteristics in patients who underwent surgery only versus those who received peri-operative chemotherapy

	All patients (n=967)			
	Total (n=967)	Peri-op. chemotherapy (n=779)	Surgery alone (n=188)	p value
<i>Patient characteristics</i>				
Age (years), median (IQR)	65.0 (58.3 to 73.1)	64.0 (57.3 to 71.7)	70.2 (62.6 to 76.7)	<0.001
Male sex, n/total (%) [*]	623/967 (64.4%)	496/779 (63.7%)	127/188 (67.6%)	0.316
ASA classification, n/total (%) [*]				
ASA I-II	598/909 (65.8%)	486/732 (66.4%)	112/177 (63.3%)	0.435
ASA III-IV	311/909 (34.2%)	246/732 (33.6%)	65/177 (36.7%)	
<i>Disease characteristics</i>				
T stage 3 or 4, n/total (%) [*]	804/921 (87.3%)	656/739 (88.8%)	148/182 (81.3%)	0.010
N stage 1 or 2, n/total (%) [*]	561/928 (60.5%)	464/736 (62.2%)	97/182 (53.3%)	0.029
Synchronous CRLM, n/total (%) [*]	525/965 (54.4%)	448/778 (57.6%)	77/187 (41.2%)	<0.001
Total bilirubin, mg/dL, mean (SD)	0.7 (0.5 to 0.9)	0.6 (0.4 to 0.8)	0.9 (0.6 to 1.1)	<0.001
Albumin, mg/dL, median (IQR)	4.2 (4.0 to 4.4)	4.2 (4.0 to 4.4)	4.1 (3.9 to 4.3)	0.233
CEA, median (IQR)	7.2 (3.0 to 25.6)	7.0 (3.0 to 25.6)	8.0 (3.9 to 26.7)	0.193
Number of CRLM, n/total (%) [*]				
Solitary	436/938 (46.5%)	304/754 (40.3%)	132/184 (71.7%)	<0.001
Multifocal	502/938 (53.5%)	450/754 (59.7%)	52/184 (28.3%)	
Size of biggest CRLM, median (IQR)	30 (20 to 45)	30 (20 to 45)	32 (21 to 45)	0.077
Location of CRLM, n/total (%) [*]				
Unilobar	428/676 (63.3%)	377/616 (61.2%)	51/60 (85.0%)	0.001
Bilobar	248/676 (36.7%)	239/616 (38.8%)	9/60 (15.0%)	
GAME score, n/total (%) [*]				
Low-risk (0 or 1 points)	669/967 (69.2%)	515/779 (66.1%)	154/188 (81.9%)	<0.001
Medium- to high-risk (≥2 points)	298/967 (30.8%)	264/779 (33.9%)	34/188 (18.1%)	
Tumor burden score (TBS), n/total (%) [*]				
Category 0	676/967 (69.9%)	524/779 (67.3%)	152/188 (80.9%)	<0.001
Category 1 or 2	291/967 (30.1%)	255/779 (32.7%)	36/188 (19.1%)	
Clinical risk score, n/total (%) [*]				
Low-risk (CRS ≤2)	488/616 (79.2%)	402/513 (78.4%)	86/103 (83.5%)	0.231
High-risk (CRS ≥3)	128/616 (20.8%)	111/513 (21.6%)	17/103 (16.5%)	
<i>Neoadjuvant chemotherapy data</i>				
Neoadjuvant treatment, n/total (%) [*]	594/778 (76.4%)	594/778 (76.4%)	NA	NA
Patients receiving at least two chemotherapy drugs, n/total (%) [†]	563/588 (95.8%)	563/588 (95.8%)	NA	NA
Patients receiving biological agents, n/total (%) [†]	290/594(48.8%)	290/594(48.8%)	NA	NA
*Denominators may differ from total sample size due to missing data				
[†] Denominator only includes patients who received neoadjuvant systemic therapy				
NA: not applicable				

Table 2 Comparison of surgical characteristics and post-operative outcomes in patients who underwent surgery only versus those who received peri-operative chemotherapy

	All patients (n=967)			
	Total (n=967)	Peri-op. chemotherapy (n=779)	Surgery alone (n=188)	p value
<i>Surgical and perioperative data</i>				
Major resection, n/total (%)*	280/964 (29.1%)	241/777 (31.0%)	39/187 (20.9%)	0.007
Associated ablative procedures, n/total (%)*	130/896 (14.5%)	120/737 (16.3%)	10/159 (6.3%)	0.002
Pringle maneuver time, median (IQR) [†]	27 (18 to 41)	30 (18 to 42)	26 (18 to 40)	0.515
Blood loss (ml), median (IQR)	300 (100 to 747)	350 (140 to 800)	300 (100 to 500)	0.055
Operative time (min), median (IQR)	210 (135 to 285)	225 (150 to 290)	160 (105 to 225)	<0.001
<i>Post-operative complications</i>				
Complications ≥ Clavien-Dindo IIIA, n/total (%)*	130/958 (13.6%)	110/771 (14.3%)	20/187 (10.7%)	0.201
Bile leakage, n/total (%)*	51/939 (5.4%)	45/764 (5.9%)	6/175 (3.4%)	0.172
Haemorrhage, n/total (%)*	21/937 (2.2%)	19/764 (2.5%)	2/173 (1.2%)	0.249
Post-operative liver failure n/total (%)*	20/936 (2.1%)	18/762 (2.4%)	2/174 (1.2%)	0.283
Intrabdominal infection, n/total (%)*	89/951 (9.4%)	74/766 (9.7%)	15/185 (8.1%)	0.509
Reoperation, n/total (%)*	48/952 (5.0%)	39/770 (5.1%)	9/182 (5.0%)	0.890
90-days mortality n/total (%)*	24/953 (2.5%)	17/771 (2.2%)	7/182 (3.8%)	0.204
LOS, median (IQR)	6 (5 to 9)	6 (5 to 9)	6 (5 to 8)	0.186
<i>Histopathological findings</i>				
R0, n (%)	594/914 (65.0%)	482/732 (65.9%)	112/182 (61.5%)	0.278
Grade, n/total (%)				
Well/moderately-differentiated	495/542 (91.3%)	450/491 (91.7%)	45/51 (88.2%)	0.429
Poorly/un-differentiated	47/542 (8.7%)	41/491 (8.3%)	6/51 (11.8%)	
K-RAS positive, n/total (%)*	178/603 (29.5%)	162/550 (29.5%)	16/53 (30.2%)	0.911
<i>Adjuvant chemotherapy</i>				
Adjuvant treatment, n/total (%)*	508/768 (66.2%)	508/768 (66.2%)	NA	NA
Patients receiving at least two chemotherapy drugs, n/total (%) [‡]	409/467 (87.6%)	409/467 (87.6%)	NA	NA
Patients receiving biological agents, n/total (%) [‡]	182/474 (38.4%)	182/474 (38.4%)	NA	NA
<i>Oncological outcomes</i>				
Follow-up (months), median	68.4	72.0	58.6	NA
Recurrence-free survival (months)				
Median (IQR)	27.0 (9.5 to 74.6)	27.0 (8.9 to 74.6)	30.0 (12.0 to 80.0)	
1-year RFS (%)	69.6%	68.4%	74.8%	0.560
3-year RFS (%)	43.6%	43.3%	45.0%	
5-year RFS (%)	30.9%	31.6%	22.8%	
Overall survival (months)				
Median (IQR)	52.0 (28.0 to NR)	52.0 (28.1 to NR)	52.5 (22.6 to NR)	
1-year OS (%)	90.6%	91.0%	88.7%	0.391
3-year OS (%)	64.6%	65.1%	62.2%	
5-year OS (%)	45.9%	46.5%	42.9%	
10-year OS (%)	30.4%	30.5%	30.2%	

*Denominators may differ from total sample size due to missing data

[†]Pringle time was calculated only for patients for whom the Pringle maneuver was used

[‡] Denominator only includes patients who received adjuvant systemic therapy

NA: not applicable; NR: not reached

Table 3: Bivariable and multivariable analysis of factors related to recurrence free survival and overall survival from the unmatched cohort.

Recurrence Free Survival						
Variable	Bivariate analysis			Multivariate analysis		
	HR	95%CI	p-Value	HR	95%CI	p-Value
Age	.995	.988-1.002	0.225			
ASA classification	1.016	.908-1.138	0.771			
Disease-free survival from CR resection	.997	.991-1.002	0.305			
T stage colorectal cancer	1.053	.927-1.197	0.423			
N stage colorectal cancer	1.201	1.090-1.323	<0.001	---	---	---
Number of lesions	1.029	1.015-1.044	<0.001	---	---	---
Size of the biggest lesion	1.002	1.001-1.003	<0.001	---	---	---
Type of resection (major vs minor)	1.130	.955-1.337	0.154			
Complications \geq Clavien-Dindo IIIA	.742	.500-1.102	0.140			
Radicality CRLM resection (R1 vs R0)	1.252	1.063-1.474	0.007	---	---	---
KRAS/BRAF mutation*	1.609	1.056-2.095	0.023	---	---	---
Perioperative chemotherapy	.5946	.449-.787	<0.001	.535	.320-.760	0.001
Overall Survival						
Variable	Bivariate analysis			Multivariate analysis		
	HR	95%CI	p-Value	HR	95%CI	p-Value
Age	1.011	1.002-1.019	0.009	---	---	---
ASA classification	1.126	.986-1.285	0.079			
Disease-free survival from CR resection	.992	.985-.998	0.015	---	---	---
T stage colorectal cancer	1.135	.977- 1.319	0.097			
N stage colorectal cancer	1.132	1.012-1.265	0.029	---	---	---
Number of lesions	1.009	.996-1.023	0.164			
Size of the biggest lesion	1.000	.999-1.002	0.220			
Type of resection (major vs minor)	1.213	1.003-1.467	0.046	---	---	---
Complications \geq Clavien-Dindo IIIA	1.445	1.004-2.081	0.047	---	---	---
Radicality CRLM resection (R1 vs R0)	1.265	1.046- 1.529	0.015	1.626	1.020-2.593	0.041
KRAS/BRAF mutation*	1.488	1.056-2.095	0.023	---	---	---
Perioperative chemotherapy	0.568	.412-.782	0.001	.644	.426-.974	0.037

*This includes patients with mutated KRAS and/or BRAF

Table 4 Comparison of baseline and preoperative characteristics in patients who underwent surgery only versus those who received peri-operative chemotherapy after PSM analysis

	Propensity-score matched cohort (n=350)		
	Peri-op. chemotherapy (n=175)	Surgery alone (n=175)	p value
<i><u>Patient characteristics</u></i>			
Age (years), median (IQR)	67.9 (61.6 to 75.3)	70.7 (63.3 to 76.8)	0.167
Male sex, n/total (%) [*]	112/175 (64.0%)	118/175 (67.4%)	0.500
ASA classification, n/total (%) [*]			
ASA I-II	110/175 (62.9%)	110/175 (62.9%)	1.000
ASA III-IV	65/175 (37.1%)	65/175 (37.1%)	
<i><u>Disease characteristics</u></i>			
T stage 3 or 4, n/total (%) [*]	142/169 (84.0%)	142/173 (82.1%)	0.662
N stage 1 or 2, n/total (%) [*]	83/171 (48.5%)	90/173 (52.0%)	0.508
Synchronous CRLM, n/total (%) [*]	66/175 (37.7%)	76/174 (43.7%)	0.293
Total bilirubin, mg/dL, mean (SD)	0.6 (0.5 to 0.9)	0.8 (0.6 to 1.1)	0.576
Albumin, mg/dL, median (IQR)	4.2 (3.9 to 4.4)	4.1 (4.0 to 4.3)	0.513
CEA, median (IQR)	6.6 (3.0 to 15.0)	8.0 (4.0 to 29.4)	0.134
Number of CRLM, n/total (%) [*]			
Solitary	115/174 (66.1%)	122/171 (71.4%)	0.293
Multifocal	59/174 (28.7%)	49/171 (28.7%)	
Size of biggest CRLM, median (IQR)	30 (20 to 50)	33 (22 to 45)	0.529
Location of CRLM, n/total (%) [*]			
Unilobar	109/134 (81.3%)	42/51 (82.4%)	0.618
Bilobar	25/134 (18.7%)	9/51 (17.7%)	
GAME score, n/total (%) [*]			
Low-risk (0 or 1 points)	141/175 (80.6%)	142/175 (81.1%)	0.886
Medium- to high-risk (≥2 points)	34/175 (19.4%)	33/175 (18.9%)	
Tumor burden score (TBS), n/total (%) [*]			
Category 0	142/175 (81.1%)	140/175 (80.0%)	0.777
Category 1 or 2	33/175 (18.9%)	35/175 (20.0%)	
Clinical risk score, n/total (%) [*]			
Low-risk (CRS ≤2)	111/129 (86.1%)	82/97 (84.5%)	1.000
High-risk (CRS ≥3)	18/129 (13.9%)	15/97 (15.5%)	
<i><u>Neoadjuvant chemotherapy data</u></i>			
Neoadjuvant treatment, n/total (%) [*]	121/175 (69.1%)	NA	NA
Patients receiving at least two chemotherapy drugs, n/total (%) ^{††}	112/119 (94.1%)	NA	NA
Patients receiving biological agents, n/total (%) ^{††}	53/121 (43.8%)	NA	NA

^{*}Denominators may differ from total sample size due to missing data
^{††} Denominator only includes patients who received neoadjuvant systemic therapy
NA: not applicable

Table 5 Comparison of surgical characteristics and post-operative outcomes in patients who underwent surgery only versus those who received peri-operative chemotherapy after PSM analysis

	Propensity-score matched cohort (n=350)		
	Peri-op. chemotherapy (n=175)	Surgery alone (n=175)	p value
<i>Surgical and perioperative data</i>			
Major resection, n/total (%)*	31/175 (17.7%)	36/175 (20.6%)	0.467
Associated ablative procedures, n/total (%)*	10/167 (6.0%)	10/148 (6.8%)	1.000
Pringle maneuver time, median (IQR) [†]	30 (17 to 45)	25 (18 to 40)	0.287
Blood loss (ml), median (IQR)	350 (100 to 800)	300 (100 to 500)	0.446
Operative time (min), median (IQR)	210 (125 to 300)	160 (105 to 225)	<0.001
<i>Post-operative complications</i>			
Complications ≥ Clavien-Dindo IIIA, n/total (%)*	22/174 (12.6%)	20/175 (11.4%)	0.758
Bile leakage, n/total (%)*	10/172 (5.8%)	5/163 (3.1%)	0.292
Haemorrhage, n/total (%)*	8/172 (4.7%)	1/162 (0.6%)	0.013
Post-operative liver failure n/total (%)*	4/171 (2.3%)	2/163 (1.2%)	0.424
Intrabdominal infection, n/total (%)*	14/172 (8.1%)	13/173 (7.5%)	0.835
Reoperation, n/total (%)*	6/174 (3.5%)	8/171 (4.7%)	0.594
90-days mortality n/total (%)*	5/173 (2.9%)	7 (4.0%)	0.566
LOS, median (IQR)	6 (5 to 9)	6 (5 to 8)	0.164
<i>Histopathological findings</i>			
R0, n (%)	108/170 (63.5%)	105/172 (61.1%)	0.553
Grade, n/total (%)			
Well/moderately-differentiated	100/116 (86.2%)	41/47 (87.2%)	1.000
Poorly/un-differentiated	16/116 (13.8%)	6/47 (12.8%)	
K-RAS positive, n/total (%)*	28/120 (23.3%)	15/47 (31.9%)	0.763
<i>Adjuvant chemotherapy</i>			
Adjuvant treatment, n/total (%)*	119/173 (68.8%)	NA	NA
Patients receiving at least two chemotherapy drugs, n/total (%) [‡]	95/111 (85.6%)	NA	NA
Patients receiving biological agents, n/total (%) [‡]	30/118 (25.4%)	NA	NA
<i>Oncological outcomes</i>			
Follow-up (months), median	74.9	58.6	NA
Recurrence-free survival (months)			
Median (IQR)	35.6 (10.0 to 93.0)	31.0 (12.1 to 72.0)	
1-year RFS (%)	72.8%	75.8%	0.209
3-year RFS (%)	49.3%	45.2%	
5-year RFS (%)	39.4%	26.7%	
Overall survival (months)			
Median (IQR)	82.8 (33.5 to 105)	52.5 (22.6 to NR)	
1-year OS (%)	90.7%	89.6%	0.017
3-year OS (%)	71.6%	62.4%	
5-year OS (%)	57.9%	41.9%	

*Denominators may differ from total sample size due to missing data

[†]Pringle time was calculated only for patients for whom the Pringle maneuver was used

[‡] Denominator only includes patients who received adjuvant systemic therapy

NA: not applicable; NR: not reached

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Marcello Di Martino